

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No. B418
 Date: 10 November 2008
 Take Off: 11:31:55Z 17:49:07Z
 Landing: 16:13:40Z 21:17:33Z
 Flight Time 4h 41m 45s 3h 28m 26s

Campaign: VOCALS – Pollution Study Flight 2

Operating Area: S.E. Pacific Ocean off the coast of northern Chile . Refuel Antofagasta

POB	Position	Name	Institute	Logs y/n
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight	
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight	
3	CCM1	Dawn Quinn	Directflight	
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office	Y
5	Mission Scientist 2	Keith Bower	Manchester University	Y
6	Flight Manager	Mo Smith	FAAM	Y
7	Core Chem	Doug Anderson	FAAM	Y
8	Cloud Physics	Martyn Pickering	Met Office	Y
9	SWS / SHIMS	Debbie O'Sullivan	Met Office	Y
10	ARIES	Stuart Rogers	Met Office	N
11	CAPS / 2DS	Hugh Coe	Manchester University	
12	AMS / CCN	Paul Williams	Manchester University	
13	Wet Neph / PSAP / Filters	James Bowles	Met Office	Y,y,y
14	VACC	Jim McQuaid	Leeds University	
15	CVI	Paul Barrett	Met Office	
16	MARSS	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Met Office	y
17	Mission Scientist 3	Jean-Louis Brenguier	EUFAR	
18	Mission Scientist 4	Mirosław Andrejczuk	Leeds University	

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No b418
 Date: 10 November 2008
 Project: VOCALS Pollution Study
 Location: Pacific Ocean off N Chile

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
094736		Start-Up	0.00 kft	019	18'21.00S, 70'20.21W
113155	113846	Profile 1	0.61 - 6.0 kft	204	T/O Arica
113422		Video	1.9 kft	249	Start x 4
120224	120924	Profile 2	6.0 - -.02 kft	007	500fpm from 1k-50'
120924	121037	Profile 3	-.02 - 0.40 kft	187	50'-500'
121037	122039	Run 1	0.40 kft	183	500', Q1016
121634		JW	0.43 kft	116	Zero cal
122040	122246	Profile 4	0.40 - 2.4 kft	184	Q1016 ,0.5k-2.5k'
122247	123341	Run 2	2.4 kft	185	2.5k'
123341	123523	Profile 5	2.4 - 3.7 kft	186	2.5k-3.8k'
123524	124524	Run 3	3.7 - 3.6 kft	183	3.8k'-3.7k' in cloud
124525	124608	Profile 6	3.6 - 4.3 kft	185	3.7k-4.4k'
124623	125047	Profile 7	4.2 - 0.40 kft	186	4.4k'-500', Q1017
125047	130048	Run 4	0.40 kft	187	500'
130048	130435	Profile 8	0.40 - 3.7 kft	188	500'-3.8k'
130435	131619	Run 5	3.7 - 3.4 kft	183	3.8k'
130522		Event	3.7 kft	185	Below Do228
130759		Adjust	3.6 kft	185	down to 3.7k'
130924		Adjust	3.5 kft	184	down to 3.5k'
131619	131804	Profile 9	3.4 - 4.8 kft	184	3.5k-4.9k'
131805	133002	Run 6	4.8 kft	182	4.9k'
133002	133613	Profile 10	4.8 - -.06 kft	115	4.9k-50', Q1019
133655	134656	Run 7	0.40 - 0.33 kft	188	500'
134318		Heimann	0.34 kft	186	Cal
134656	135041	Profile 11	0.33 - 3.4 kft	186	500'-3.5k'
135042	140042	Run 8	3.4 - 3.3 kft	185	3.5k'
135604		Adjust	3.3 kft	185	down to 3.4k'
140042	140118	Profile 12.1	3.3 - 3.8 kft	184	3.4k-3.8k'
140118	140620	Profile 12.2	3.8 - -.07 kft	184	3.8k-50'
140655	150449	Run 9	0.35 - 0.40 kft	188	500'
140819		Event	0.35 kft	188	At P2
142238		Heimann	0.36 kft	025	Cal
145521		Heimann	0.39 kft	022	Cal
150449	150840	Profile 13	0.40 - 3.6 kft	027	500'-3.7k'
150841	152339	Run 10	3.6 kft	188	3.7k', In cloud
152339	152433	Profile 14.1	3.6 - 4.2 kft	201	3.7k-4.3k' Q1015
152433	152731	Profile 14.2	4.2 - 1.4 kft	202	4.3k-1.5k'
152731	153012	Profile 14.3	1.4 - 3.6 kft	202	1.5k'-3.7k'
153012	154510	Run 11	3.6 - 3.4 kft	203	3.7k'
154309		Adjust	3.3 kft	201	down to 3.5k'
154604	154642	Profile 15.1	3.4 - 3.8 kft	083	3.5k-4k'
154643	154911	Profile 15.2	3.8 - 1.5 kft	080	4k'-1.5k'
154912	155115	Profile 15.3	1.4 - 3.3 kft	082	1.5k'-3.5k'
155116	155532	Run 12	3.3 - 3.4 kft	100	3.5k'
161340		Land	0.32 kft	119	Antofagasta
161441		ASP	0.33 kft	101	Closed
161709		Shutdown	0.32 kft	096	23'26.88S, 70'26.50W Refuel
174311		ASP	0.35 kft	269	Open
174907		T/O	2.1 kft	341	Antofagasta
175316	181104	Run 13	6.0 - 5.9 kft	336	
175700		Video	6.0 kft	333	
181104	181804	Profile 16	5.9 - 0.02 kft	303	To 50', Q1016
181838	182907	Run 14	0.47 - 0.51 kft	274	500'
182908	183309	Profile 17	0.51 - 4.3 kft	288	500'-4.3k'
183309	183414	Profile 18	4.3 - 3.5 kft	282	4.3k'-3.5k'
183414	184422	Run 15	3.5 kft	044	3.5k'
184422	184745	Profile 19	3.5 - 0.43 kft	072	3.5k'- 500',
184745	185752	Run 16	0.43 - 0.53 kft	069	500'

185659		Heimann	0.46 kft	069 Cal
185752	190147	Profile 20	0.53 - 3.9 kft	068 500'-4.2k'
190147	190237	Profile 21	3.9 - 3.5 kft	306 4.2k-3.6k'
190237	191240	Run 17	3.5 kft	302 3.6k'
190326		Adjust	3.6 kft	300 down to 3.5k'
191240	191624	Profile 22	3.5 - 0.47 kft	303 3.5k'-500'
191624	192631	Run 18	0.47 - 0.50 kft	307 500'
192316		Heimann	0.44 kft	304 Cal
192631	193003	Profile 23	0.50 - 4.1 kft	305 500- 4.2k'
193004	193115	Profile 24	4.1 - 3.5 kft	070 4.2k'-3.5k'
193115	193950	Run 19	3.5 - 3.4 kft	075 3.5k'
193418		Adjust	3.4 kft	075 down to 3.4k'
193918		JW	3.4 kft	072 Zero Cal
193951	194216	Profile 25	3.4 - 4.7 kft	072 3.4k-4.8k'
194217	194745	Profile 26	4.7 - 0.48 kft	070 4.8k'-500'
194745	201226	Run 20.1	0.48 - 0.53 kft	070 500', Q1015
195620		Heimann	0.54 kft	282 Cal
201320	203048	Run 20.2	0.55 - 0.46 kft	064 500'
201346		Heimann	0.48 kft	071 Cal
203151	204808	Run 20.3	0.45 - 0.48 kft	183 500', Find plume edge
203930		Heimann	0.48 kft	182 Cal
204911	205004	Profile 27.1	0.44 - 0.05 kft	026 500-50'
205004	205439	Profile 27.2	0.05 - 5.0 kft	026 50'-5k'
211733		Land	0.16 kft	109 Arica
211900		ASP	0.17 kft	111 Closed
211938		Shutdown	0.16 kft	022 18'21.00S, 70'20.21W

B418 Track 10-NOV-08

**FAAM Sortie, Flight B418 - VOCALS Pollution Plume.
Mon 10th November 2008**

T/O - 0830 local (1130 UTC).
Land Antofagasta - 1230 local (1530 UTC)
T/O Antofagasta - 1400 local (1700 UTC)
Land - 1700 local (2000 UTC)

Mission Scientists: Phil Brown plus Keith Bower

Operating Area: SE Pacific Ocean, off west coast of northern Chile.

Waypoints:	P1	19 00'S	72 00'W
	P2	24 30'S	74 40'W
	P3	22 30'S	71 40'W
	P4	23 30'S	71 30'W
	P5	22 00'S	74 30'W

Sortie Objectives: To sample aerosol microphysics and chemistry together with aerosol-cloud interactions in the region of a pollution plume moving northwards up the coast from central Chile.

Coordination with other aircraft: Do228 will operate at FL150 along track P1-P2, taking off shortly before the 146.

Latest satellite Image (to be inserted):

Detailed Flight schedule: PTO

Key Instrument Details:

SWS – as per instructions.

ARIES – as per instructions

CVI - During high level operate in aerosol mode with CVI hygrometer operating.

CVI – during in cloud runs operate in counterflow mode : **AMS** and **SMPS** to sample from it

Wet Neph – operated during all of low level non-cloud runs

AMS – operate from Rosemount during aerosol and high level runs and profiles; operate on CVI during in cloud runs

Filters – Vent the inlet line in the absence of filter immediately after cloud runs. Then expose filters as required by Miss.Sci2.

Flight Summary:

1. Take off and profile ascent 1000 ft/min immediately to 6000ft amsl. Continue transit towards P1. At P1, turn on track to P2.
2. Commence cycle of profile descent 1000ft/min to 50ft amsl followed by 10 min straight/level legs at altitudes:
 - a. 500ft amsl
 - b. 500ft below cloud base.
 - c. 300ft below cloud top.
 - d. Ascent to 1000ft above cloud top.
3. Repeat item 2 along track towards P2. Arrange coordination with Do228 via 123.45MHz or Satcom so that 146 is in cloud when it underflies the Do228 along track to P2.
4. At P2, profile descent to 50ft amsl, and then straight level leg at 500ft amsl heading towards P3.
5. From P3, profile ascent 100ft/min to 1000ft above cloud or inversion top.
6. Straight/level leg returning to P2 at an altitude of 300ft below cloud top. Adjust height along run if necessary to maintain cloud-top relative altitude.
7. Recover to Antofagasta to refuel.
8. Takeoff from Antofagasta and profile ascent 1000ft/min to 6000ft amsl towards P4.
9. Repeat item 2 on track towards P4, and continue towards P5.
10. Repeat item 2 on return track towards P4.
11. Profile ascent 1000ft/min from P4 to FL230 on return heading to Arica.
12. Return transit with profile descent from FL230 to arrive point ORCAS at 5000ft.
13. Land Arica.

BAe146 Mission Scientist debrief:

11 Nov 2008

Flight B418

Coastal Pollution Plumes

Philip R.A. Brown

Sortie Objectives:

To complete below- and in-cloud sampling in the region of pollution plumes moving in the southerly flow up the coast from central Chile.

Takeoff	1132 U
Land	1614 UT (Antofagasta)
Takeoff	1745 UT
Land	2115 UT (Arica)

Waypoints:	P1	19 00'S	72 00'W
	P2	24 30'S	74 40'W
	P3	22 30'S	71 40'W
	P6	22 00'S	72 30'W
	P7	21 30'S	71 00'W
	P8	20 30'S	72 30'W
	P9	20 00'S	71 00'W
	P10	19 30'S	72 30'W

Flight Track

Cloud conditions:

Fig 1. GOES 10 visible image at 1315 UT

Fig.2 GOES 10 visible image at 2015 UT

Cloud-free at Arica on takeoff. Extensive quasi-homogeneous Sc along the southerly leg from P1 to P2. Cloud gradually thinning and breaking up during the day, most obviously around 20S 71W. The intention was to transit across a pollution plume identified earlier in the day from GOES BT differences along the track from P2-P3. Sulphate aerosol was observed throughout this region although without an obvious plume maximum.

Mission profile:

1. Climb out from Arica to 6000ft heading towards point P1. Profile descent 1000ft/min to 50ft amsl.
2. On track P1-P2, completed a number of 10 min legs in sets 500ft amsl and in cloud. During 1st set an additional leg at 2500ft amsl was also completed prior to the in-cloud leg. On this leg, small breaks in cloud observed to the east. Light surface winds with no whitecapping.
3. A total of 4*500ft and 3*in-cloud legs were completed. Cloud legs at 3600ft, 3700 decreasing to 3500ft, 3400 decreasing to 3300ft – reflecting the lower inversion height further to the south. Typical cloud droplet concentrations 250cm⁻³ with mean diameter ~15 μ m. Typical PCASP aerosol concentrations ~180 cm⁻³. Sulphate aerosol observed throughout. CCN at 0.1% ~120 cm⁻³, CNC ~ 750 cm⁻³.
4. After 1st in-cloud leg windscreen had a thin whiteish deposit – possibly sea-salt or dust from cloud droplets.
5. From P2 a leg at 500ft amsl all the way to P3. CCN ~60 cm⁻³ at 0.1% near P2.
6. From P3 a leg in cloud heading towards P3. This was flown as approx 10 min segments in cloud with profile ascents/descents in between to determine cloud top and base changes along the leg. In cloud segments were flown at altitudes of 3600ft, 3400 descending to 3300ft and 3500ft. Cloud conditions typically

- cumulus below Sc. LWC showed significant peaks during passage through regions where Cu penetrating into Sc layer.
7. Sulphate aerosol observed throughout but generally higher to the east of 72W. Increasing accumulation mode contributions observed by increasing differential scattering in nephelometer.
 8. from the end of the last in-cloud segment, transit above cloud to land and refuel at Antofagasta. Cloud edge located to the west of Antofagasta, but with a region of lower patchy stratus within the boundary layer and substantial haze remaining up to the marine boundary layer top.
 9. After t/o from Antofagasta, profile ascent to 6000ft amsl and then descend to 50ft amsl on track to P6.
 10. Two 10-min straight/level legs at 500ft amsl and 3500ft in-cloud.
 11. On track from P6 to P7, two 10-min straight/level legs at 500ft amsl and 3600ft in-cloud.
 12. On track from P7 to P8, two 10-min straight/level legs at 500ft amsl and 3400ft in-cloud.
 13. On track from P8 to P9, two 10-min straight/level legs at 500ft amsl and 3500ft in-cloud. Sc observed to be much more thin and patchy around P9.
 14. On track from P9 to P10, whole leg completed at 500ft amsl due to the break-up of cloud ahead. Aircraft observed to be flying approximately parallel to the northern edge of a larger rift in the cloud extending out to the west. Near the start of this track in a position around 20 00 S 71 30W significantly higher loadings of sulphate aerosol were observed approaching $\sim 15\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ (of sulphuric acid).
 15. Track from P10 at 500ft completed but high plume concentrations were not observed. Diversion remaining at 500ft amsl back towards the 20S 71 30W position in an attempt to relocate the plume. This was successful.
 16. Profile ascent at 1000ft/min from 50ft to 5000ft amsl on return track towards Arica.

Overall summary

The pollution plume identified early in the day from GOES-10 BT differences was probably not intercepted although a narrow plume with higher sulphate loadings was intercepted further to the north. Sulphate aerosol observed throughout but more generally closer to the coast. The flight was considered to be a useful survey of the boundary layer structure and cloud conditions in the near-coastal region to the south of Arica, on a day when the cloud was observed initially to be quite homogeneous. The boundary layer vertical profile was typically cumulus under Sc throughout the flight.

1 Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 418 Date 10/11/08 Name Phil Brown Page 1 of 9

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
1130	P1				t/o 2 profile P1.
/					clear of cloud, haze patch low N of city
/					Stable sp. boundary layer at ARI, with upper mixed layer
1146		6000		18 300 71 60W	just approaching cloud edge in Arica flight
/					Haze layers above
/					- probably just above this level
115425		"			Note varying Td along this run - -25 to +1 °C
/					Do. B 1202 E 1348 1348
1204					in P2, Co penetration to both
/		3800			tops.
/		3200			base. seems ill-defined
120924		50		18 48S 71 54W	end P2 back to 500ft
121037		500			Start 1 orbiting again to N P2 cloud layer decoupled.
121945		1016 500		14 S 72W	passing Point 1
122039		"			end R1 start P4
122247		2500			Start R2 small breaks in cloud to E.
1233					lighter fc wind here - no whitecapping. 155/4ms' a bit.
		3000			base
123524		3700			R3 3500 was still in cloud.
					CNP 250N 15-16µm 200

MF 550 → 576 10L-2DC
420 200µm was.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 418 Date 10/11/08 Name Phil Brown Page 2 of 9

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
1244				Note	TW & Neoz now widely sep again, as expected in high core, low diam condns.
124525		3700			end R3
/		4100			tops P7 faintly well mixed.
/		2900			base
125047		⁰¹⁷ 500			Ru-4 ^{windscreen deposit} picked up in cloud. white, dusty? photos
/					180 RASP CW1
/					AMS sulphate reduced since cloud.
/					CAN 120/750 0.1%
130048				21 24 S 72 12 W	end R4 & profile into cloud.
		2600			base.
130435		3800			start R5 20sec to Laminar underfly.
130744		3700			easing to 3700
130905		3500			easing down.
/					COP → 300 Hz 100 V 5 2DC MF 600 15 200 per max
131619		"			end R5
		.			3800 tops
1318		4900			level for a break.
1320		"			high CO?
133002		" ↓			start P10
		3800			tops
/		3100			base but some lower
-					bases around.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 418 Date 10/11/08 Name Paul Brown Page 3 of 9

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
/		10ft 500			more visibility, but more whitecapping.
133613		50ft			P10 end
133655		500ft		22 42.0 72 24.0	R7 eta pt 2 1410
/					172 / 9 ms ⁻¹
/					note most near surface in P10. Structure corresponding to regions of lower cloudbase.
/					Nephelaw - larger ptclcs
/					slightly lower scattering
					1000 cu, P10SP
1343					can 90/900 @ 0.1% D at E
/					AMS - biculplate on 1st part of run.
/					CAS course mode - not seen before
134656		//			end R67e profile to in cloud.
		2650			in base but some lower.
		3800			tops +/- 50ft
135042		3500		23 30S 72 20W	Start R8 in cloud.
/					P11 looks well mixed
					COP 200 - 19µm 200 10-100 MF 300 18 250µm
1355		3400			decreasing total aerosol concn S, but more coarse mode due to higher wind speeds.
/					700 CPC end R8
140042					tops
		3600			P12 definite double structure in LWC
/					more stuff on windscreen
/					whiterish?

140620 50ft end P12
140655 500ft. start R9

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 418 Date 10/11/08 Name Pan Brown Page 4 of 9

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
140826		500ft			R9 in turn at pt 2
					AMS: bimodal 120 & 55nm
					55/800 CCN
/					sulphate 1/ug no organics.
/					190/5ms ⁻¹
/					CVI 700 CFC. VACC agrees.
1415					Neph. - larger coarse mode
/					deaminates scattering. low sulphate.
1424					195/6ms ⁻¹ AMS still reports v. clean
1427					slowly increasing CCN & CVC
142841					Neph coarse mode slightly larger.
/					Cu visible below Sc base to the E.
/					oculr drizzle below Cu.
1438		//		22 48 S 71 48 W	her. accom. mode, sulphate.
/					revised weight. 21 CG' effect 71 62W
1444					Increasing split in Neph last 5mins.
1446					sulphate increasing. no organics
					205/5ms ⁻¹
					TWC possibly clipping
/					- need window clean.
1453					drizzle drops.
1455					Zero wind.
					CVI reduced.
/					Neph peak ~ 1445-1450
					22.5-22.8.

150449
18km

21 18 S - Run 9
71 6 W

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 418 Date 10/11/08 Name Patricia Brown Page 5 of 9

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
		3950			tops
150840	10	3700		21 24S 71 12W	short R10
1512					CSP 200 4 200 R11 MF 400 14-15 1500m
1514					LWC patch 2 v 0.45 near top that then steady 0.2
1517					LWC 0.5-0.6
/					Note N TWC dipping 0.5
					N LWC = TW in highest LWC patch
152339		4100			R10 v 0.7. tops Cu penetrates vid. ahead.
		2700			main base Cu below 1615 eta Auto.
		1700			Cu base.
15273	14.3	1500			profile min had 2 to 3700
153012	11	3700			R11
1535					LWC steadily here after Cu at start. but N TWC & N LWC more sp lit than previous steady LWC
/					? droplet size
154245		3500			adjust. as just at top.
154510				23.5S	R11 in turn in cloud.
	15.1	3700			tops, change in albedo? ahead?
		2700			base
/		1500			Cu base is lower here
155116	12	3500		23 24S 71 12W	R12
1553		//			v. lit in cloud here, near base.
155532					end 12
		3800			tops.
1600					over cloud edge.

1602 3500

1132-1613 sector
4h 41

on descent into Auto.
hazy in top of BL, patchy
Cu/Sc below the original BL top.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci 1

PHIL BROWN

Flight No **B**.....**418**.....

Date **10/11/08**.....

Page **6** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
1745					T/O ANTIF.
/		3000			cloud tops on climbout.
/					this was also the bl top
/					patchy Cu forming on coast.
175316		6000			end P. e about R13
181104		" ↓			P16
		1200			tops
		2700			base . 100L-1 2DC
181804		50			
		500			Rov-14 Extensive Cu below
/					Se. surface e cloud mixed layers
1826					Neph traces overlapping.
					200 / 9 ms ⁻¹
182908			↗ NW	2205 72.12W	end 14 , P17
		2100			base Cu,
/		3200			Se base .
		3700			tops
183414		3500			Start R15 on NE hdg in turn at about.
					AMS on prev leg 2-2.5 µg SO ₄
/					CPC 1300 CEN 400 @ 0.4
1843					OCN cloud breaks.
/					Se base still ~ 3200
					high LWC due to Cu penetration.
184622					End 15.

Mission Scientist's Log

M. Sci. - 1

Flight No **B.418**.....

Date 10/11/08.....

Page 7 of 9

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
184745		500ft			End P19. Start R16
184930		"			Sc almost gone, but nice field of Cu. 185/6ms ²
185330		"			Clear patch ahead & right but thick ahead/left. poss drizzle on track
185752		500ft		21 24 S 71. W	End 16, P20
		2700			Sc edge to N of turn pt. above Cu base.
		3400			base.
		3700			tops.
190237		3600			run 17
190330		3500			cloud thin
					COP 220 12pm 15' ocean MF 450 11pm. <100pm.
					AMS
1910		"			LWC mostly <0.1 but peaks at 0.3 in Cu penetrations
191240				20 54 S 71 48 W	end 17, P22
191624		500			R-18. 0.2 gm profiles near well mixed.
192631		"		20 24 S 72 30 W	end 18 turn & profile.
					Neph scattering looks similar on last 2 low levels.
					AMS 8-9 µg at E
		3200	base		- 5.8 at W.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.418**.....

Date

Page **8** of **9**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
		3700			tops.
193115		3500			start R2 B19
				Clear	decoupled structure in P23
193402		3400			CDP - 250 - slow rise 12m MF 450 12m
—					20C 11-1 50-75 μ m
19395					end 19 - clear below now.
19427		4800	N		P26
19445					ARIES out of disk space.
					wind 170/4, but more
194745	20	start ⁵⁰⁰			whitecapping here,
					perhaps windspeed is greater
—					due to coastal jet.
				20 S 71 12W	206/7 now.
—					15 μ g SO ₄ current.
					AMS. 30 μ g peak.
					2 μ g ammonium.
2000					cloud ahead again.
2005					still 10 μ g SO ₄ AMS.
200530					Appear to be running 11el
		1015 500	cut his leg		to orienter of main cloud
2011					break.
—					CVI 750 peak in plane.
					now 200
201226		500			end 20.1
					start 20.2
					160/5 ms ⁻¹

2023

11

Neph scattering increasing again.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...418 Date 10/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 1 of 4

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
11:24 ish					Do 228 T/O
11:25:30					Twainy
11:31.17					Rolling
11:31.53	P1				T/O
11:35.44	P1end				Do 228 is 15 miles ahead of us proceed to P1 - then allow Do 228 to get ahead of us. ETA 20mins to P1 - Buyer no other software on PC
11:47.31			244	18°36'/71°12'	Over cloud edge here
12:01.19					P1 holding - passed Do 228
12:02:26	P2	6.0kft		18°54'/72°0'	descend 811mb 16.15/-5.88° 3ms/7°
12:04:40	P2	3.8kft			CT 801mb
12:05:28	P2	3.0kft	7	18°42'/72°	CB 906mb
12:09:23	P2/P3	50ft	166	18°48'/71°54'	1013mb 18.11/13.4
12:10:43	P3/P1	0.3kft		18°54'/72°0'	500ft 904mb 18°15'/164° 16.99/12.97° Fakes on - VAEI on
12:20.41	P1end/P4	0.3kft			500ft ↑
12:22.45	P1end/P2	2.4kft	165	18°6'/72°0'	2500ft - in cloud
12:29.21	P2end/P5				
12:35.22	P5end/P3	3.7kft			3900ft ↓ to 3700ft to be in cloud SO ₂ ~ 4μg/m ³ (higher since 12:10) SMPS min N ₂ O P1 → Lec jump in record Core Cloud CDP 250 cm ⁻³ decreasing to 20 @ 15-16 ↑ 17 ESSR 550 ↓ → 420 @ 15-16 μm

dazzle 10/1 @ 200 μm

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 416 A Date 10/11/06 Name K.N. BOWER Page 2 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	R3 ⁰²⁴ / P6				
12.06.16	P6a / P7				
12.50.49	P3/ R4	0.3 hL	157	20°48/71°12'	500ft 999mb 15.87/11.34 8ms/163
					picked up yellow shell on screen
					180-190 PCASP on CNT
					SO ₂ falling away - scattering by Neph the same
					CNT - PCASP - small ice in N° / CN too
					SMPS - broad mode - dt 100-umatched
					one - close to CN CIC
					CN / CN - 120 / 750 0.1%
13:00	R4/ P6				
					Windspeed lower pressure no drum PL (2DS)
					mega sea salt - SMPS
13.03.05	P5/	2.6 hL			CB 921mb
13.04.38	P5				3500ft
13.05.30	P5				below D ₀ 228
13.07:45	P5	3.5 hL			in CT's with 100- dropping down to 3700
					6 sig in CT
					2DS N°Caro/LUC falling away
					3700 → 3500ft

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...418A Date 10/11/08 Name K. N. BOWER Page 3 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
13:10.00					CDP Drwn N↑ 300 φ K
					FSSD 600 φ 15
					ZDC 100 φ 5 in 5mins onl 20µm
13:16:19	RSend/PA.1				
					22S 74.30 17:30
					RS
13:17.57	PAend/RL	4.8 kft		22°24' / 72°20'	4800ft
13:20.30					Highed CD - 39 prob
13:24.01	RL				Holding Pattern
13:30.01	RLend/PID	4.8 kft		22°16' / 72°24'	9 m/s / 134° 19.1 K / 22.36° -
13:31.19	PID	3.6 kft			CT 856 mb
13:32.20	PID	2.6 kft		22°24' / 72°24'	CB just above here
					Do 22S pas 27 min 19 m/s
13:36.12	PIDend	5.0 kft	188	22°42' / 72°24'	9 m/s / 175° 10.15 mb 16.72°C / 11.5°
13:36.55	RTJ	5.0 kft / 0.3kt	188	22°42' / 72°24'	10 m/s / 170 998 mb 15.36 / 10.55
					PT2est 14.10
					Stronger Ste Winds here - white caping - higher sea swell
					Evidence large perturbations North - South Cells
					22.5-23 - large perturbation S 21.
					VAccl CVC 750 CVI - 1000
					Janic CN sum
					Do passal Echo -

13:32 - CCN to air leg. 90/900
AMS earlier in satellite

Som turns 22 30 71:40 W
at.
ZDS -

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B...418A Date 10/11/08 Name K. N. BOWER Page 4 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	P7/P11				2DS - evidence - coarse mode particle on CAS
13.46.57	P7/P11	0.3M/500ft		23°12'/72°30'	1001 mb 9m/s/166' 15.17/10.2°C
13.	P11 km				↓
13.50.25	P11	3.5kft			CT
13.50.42	P11 and P8	3.5kft 3.3kft			in dead run 3500ft
13.55.56	P8				ODP - ~200 ϕ - 10-20 μ m PSS - ~300 ϕ - Amogh - level 10 - 100/l 200 μ m
14.00.42	P8/P12.1	3.2kft			
14.01.18	P12.2 and				CT 3600ft cap
14.01.57	P12.2	3.5kft	185	24°6'/72°30'	CT. p 890mb 7.97°/-12.84°C 9m/s/163'
					Shut on Vinderaan again
					CB missed
14.06.58	P9 st.	500ft	188	24°24'/72°30'	1000 mb 14.32°/10.94°C 9m/s/171'
14.08.19	P9	500ft			Point P2 - down P2 → P3 @ 500ft Binned Aerosol 120 SS mm SS/800 CON/CN AMS - SO ₄ 1.0 μ g/m ³ not too much in Org. 2DS - Aerosol getting larger - all salt particles getting larger - O ₃ near 500ft

N21 - down by Ae SO₄

S21 - 1st run - coarse mode down area -
SID 21.5

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 418A Date 10/11/08 Name K.N. BOWEN Page 5 of 11.....

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					AMS - ves clear stable polluted air
14.26.22					Small wis in CPC core - CVI
					CO ↑ } by smaller PdB O ₃ ↑ }
14.28.28				2	CO
14.28.51	R	0.3kt	26	25°18'/72°6'	WOWNA B.2 / 11.44°C 7ms/193
					Cirrus Cloud - Odd drizzle patch here
					Area slightly more Cu a
					According to peaks in CO, O ₃ etc peaks at about
14.28.51	R9	0.3kt			- small patches ↑ 2PS scrub ↑ - part plain O ₃ CO ↓
					(21.05 S 71.02.14 W) Cloud Mt.
14.40.54					Nearby going blue over red - small fish stuck in - or BL
14.43.00					hit by plume SUC ↑ - no O ₃
14.55.51					Drizzle
					hit in scattering here - rather grey up
					- synched Acc mode comes 72-71.5W
					feeding among CCN/CAT 160/1000 on w!
					by 72W - Went off

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 418 A Date 10/11/08 Name K. N. BOWER Page 6 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
	R9a				
15.08.49	P13/R10	3.5kt	188	21°24'/71°12'	899mb 2m/s/107' 7.31'/15.88' 3700ft
					CPO 200 cm ⁻³ ϕ ranging 14
					FSSP 400 cm ⁻³ ϕ 14-15 μm
					droplet 10 l 150 μm max
15.19:02	R10				Hd Wtr pwr LWC ↑ seems less TW, W _w
					+ CAS
15.20.58					CAS drop N ^o ↓ again now
15.23.39	R10end/P14				3600 ↑
					CT 3900
15.26.28	P14.1/P14.2	4.1kt			
	P14.2				CB+ 2.4kt
15.27.31	P14.2end/P14.3	1.4kt	202	21°30' 71°31'	1500ft ↑
15.30.11	P14.3/R11	3.5kt	203	22°30'/71°42'	3700ft 890mb 8.05/9.37 7m/156°
15.32.45					passed P3
					VACC CPC 650 → 700
15.44.51	R11end/Turn	3.7kt			3500ft
15.46.01	P15.1/sl				Start w.
15.46.35	P15.2 ↓				Turn
15.49.11	P15.2end/P15.3	1.4kt	82	23°24'/71°48'	4 t 3500ft undet.
15.51.14	P15.3end/R11	3.7kt	94	23°24'/71°42'	3500ft undet max 6 AP
15.55.30	R12end	3.3 kt			3500ft - Reconnect AP
					CT 3850ft Contain
16.13.30	Land				

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 418b Date 10/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 7 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
17:42:12					Taxing
17:48:37					Rolling
17:49:06					T/O
		3.7kft			CB
17:53:16	und/P/RB	6kft		2312/7013	812mb 20.37/-28.32 4m/s/272
					30µg SO ₄ at alt
18:10:58	und/P	5.9kft			6000ft →
18:12:28	P16	4.2kft			C1
					see drizzle showing on window
					Circ cloud 100 CDP - φ 15
					(up to 300 200 PBR φ 20
					drizzle ~ 80 l/min - 300µm
18:14:08	P16	2.7kft			CB
18:18:05	P16und	30ft			
18:18:38	RK1	500ft (0.4kft)		22°12'/71°36'	10m/s/191 991mb 15.6/12.6°C
					223 72.30 W NW
					21 30 71 W NE
					20 30 → 22.30 W NW
					20 → 71.5 NE
					19.30 72.30 NW → Of obs
18:28:40				22°/72°12'	Break in cloud ahead
18:29:05	RKund/P17	500ft		22°/	
18:31:47	P17	2.7kft			CB - main CP
					C1
18:33:07	P17/P14				Top

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 418B Date 10/11/08 Name K. N. BOWEN Page 8 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
18.33.55	P18	3.6kft			CT
18.34.15	R15	3.4kft		21°54'/12°90'	Start'd run 893mb 4m/s/161'
					AMS - mottle SO ₂ 2-25 μg/m ³
					NO _x 1 μg/m ³ and org
					CPC 1300' CON 0.4% 900
					Salt: 10-25 / Mn
18.44.22	R15 P19				↓ to 500ft
18.47.45	P19 R16				500ft
		0.4kft			Map.
18.57.43	R16/P20	0.5kft	67	21°30'/71'	4 450ft. 994mb 3m/s/206 16.02/12.74°C
19.00.36	P20	2.1kft	202	21°24'	CB
19.01.36					CT
19.01.47	R20/O21				Top
19.02.37	R21/ R17	3.5kft			
19.03.14	R17 cont.	3.5kft		71°12'/21°18'	↓ in CT gray down 100ft
19.06.50					CDP 220 φ 12 μ
					FSSP 450 φ 11 μ
					droplet had peak 10 μ ² now 1 μ ² ~ < 100 μm
					CAS φ ~ 10 or below. N
					LWC variable and low 0.15 in 10g thru
					Split in Neph Scully MSol on Nav.
					(primarily on polluted side of boundary) MC
					MC _{oil} ⇒ Acc made see
19.12.37	R17/ R22				3500 → 500ft
					in ± 1 mb when needed.

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B.....^{418B} Date^{10/11/08} Name^{K.N. BOWEN} Page⁹ of¹¹

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					W
19.16.26	P22/P18	0.4kt	307	20°45'/71°54'	500ft 1564/16.05C Sinc/P22 996-6
					Cloud above looks to be not so blue
19.26.27	P18/P23				Clouds
					2DS Ae looking - pretty across whole leg and previous - poss evidence slightly
					high E end 8-9 μg W end 5-6 μg
19.30.03	P23/P24	4.1kt			→ 3500ft from 4200ft
19.31.15	P24/P19	3.4kt	75	20°24'/72°12'	3500ft
19.34.10	P19				drooping W of ft. all over
					CC CDP N good rising 250cm ² φ 12 PSSP N ~ 450 φ 12
					Drizzle low 1/10ths to max 50-75 μm
					2DS all over + coarse mode Ae - similar
					LWC's 0.2 (randomly 0.1 at times)
					hd mix similar
19.39.40	P19/P25	3.3kt			3400ft ↑
19.42.15	P25/P26	4.7kt			4500ft ↓
19.47.45	P26/P20				500ft Humax Screens Cond
					2DS - more material at top of BL than low (AMS and Neoh)
					CO ₂ Symp ² read as O ₃ 27 in BL
					SO ₂ 15, 16, 17 min at 500ft level

ARIES left peak - dust hdl.

25, 30 μg at BL top out of AE

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B 418B Date 10/11/08 Name K.N. BOWER Page 10 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					Scattering on Neph ↑ a bit
					plane starting at 71.3 falling away now
					Scattering peaked 30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ SO_4
					2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ NH_3 - real acid !!
20:04:53					MECH fallen off - but still pulled
					AMS 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ - can get back bounds
					ASCA - to get up plane again
					0.1 & 0.4 % SS CAN stressless
					(dropping after side of Acc mode)
					(using 1015 sub from start of run)
					PCASP - started in 1400 → end 2300
20.11.20					(altitude now 900)
					OVI - PCASP - peaked 750 in plane
	R20.1				now 250
					trailing trailing parallel to dead edge - see sat
					ri
20 12 25	R20.1	0.5kt			↖ NW
20 13 20	R20.2	0.5kt			↗ NE
20.26.12					SO_4 12 - 12.5 μg
					SMPS - strongly bunched <100 150-200
					- compare to volume → base ↑ - alt
20.30.47	R20.2	0.5kt			mode size smaller. } going S
20 31.54	R20.3	0.5kt	181°	19° 21' 24"	997 17.18 / 12.16 °C Smks / 174°

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B. 418B Date 10/11/08 Name K. N. BOWER Page 11 of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations
					(cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					1700 p 1600 CW
					500 250 CW
					CO larger range than the S zone
					background
					shape CO across gis/zys - not seen by
					Neph
					S zones
					SO ₂ - 20µg/m ³
					CFC's - some shown on PCASO
					1100 on CWI from 750
					retrograde motion at 0.4% to 50%
					10% at at 0.1% (acc)
					(alt too)
					PCASO B / CFC
20.44.07					
20.49.11	P27.1				↓ SO ₂
20.50.07	P27.2	SO ₂			↑
20.52.37					CB = 2800
20.53.17					CT. 3500
20.54.37	P27.2a	4.9kft			5000 ft
21.17.30	Landed				

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No B..... 418 Date 10/11/08 Name Ken Bowen Page Ex of 11

Time (GMT)	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks / Observations (cloud type & amount in oktas, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.) eg Cirrus 2/8, StratoCu 3/8, hazy, wind 240°/24kts
					<u>Debrief:-</u>
	<u>not sure</u>	<u>saw</u>	<u>plume on</u>	<u>P1 → P2 -</u>	<u>signs W of FLW down P2-P3?</u>
					<u>and back</u>
					<u>- maybe too far aft and or near to S</u>
					<u>& main plume</u>
	<u>have a nice survey of</u>	<u>BL</u>	<u>char</u>	<u>gain</u>	<u>S - long leg in dead and back</u>
	<u>marks</u>	<u>accounted</u>	<u>BL -</u>	<u>On</u>	<u>near</u>
					<u>Sc</u>
	<u>On way back -</u>	<u>zig zag</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>watch</u>	<u>quite</u>
					<u>and for</u>
					<u>the structure at SDEH</u>
					<u>& land structure to -</u>
	<u>On last outland -</u>	<u>passed</u>	<u>in</u>	<u>blot</u>	<u>SDEH -</u>
					<u>didn't</u>
					<u>come</u>
					<u>up</u>
					<u>near</u>
					<u>or</u>
					<u>low</u>
					<u>NE</u>
					<u>leg -</u>
					<u>found</u>
					<u>it</u>
					<u>as</u>
					<u>expected -</u>
					<u>traverse</u>
					<u>with</u>
					<u>BTing</u>
					<u>etc</u>
					<u>being</u>
					<u>at</u>
					<u>modelling</u>
					<u>date</u>
<u>?</u>	<u>Modelling</u>	<u>successful</u>	<u>investigation</u>		<u>Drop</u>
					<u>ones</u>
					<u>for</u>
					<u>CDF -</u>
					<u>200-250</u>
					<u>on?</u>
					<u>hubs</u>
					<u>described</u>
					<u>near</u>
					<u>to</u>
					<u>cont</u>
					<u>exact</u>
					<u>in</u>
					<u>POC</u>
					<u>←</u>
					<u>Check</u>
					<u>FSSP</u>

CVI ✓ fine

fillies ✓ OK

neph ✓

wid neph ✓

snts ✓

AMS ✓

core dem ✓

core dem - PCASO

+ HD failure on FFSSP just before end of a run is dead.

ARIES - run out

MARS ✓ hr

SWS - ✓ demand time down flight.

CCN ✓ partial down ✓

VACC plop - scheduled down.

↳ OPC line good agreement across all

PAN - last group - out of gas

ZDS ✓

CAOS ✓

SMPS ✓

Tomorrow - van lesson day -

- - goods ✓

Chemistry Log

Date: _____ Flight: **B418** Operator: **Doug Anderson** Page **1 of 2**

Preflight

No.	? or x	Location	Action	Comments
<u>Gases</u>				
1	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
2	X	CO ₂ / Ar	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi	160 bar – 160 bar at end of flight
3	X	Nitrogen	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
4	X	Nitrogen	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	30 bar / 20 bar at end of flight
5	X	CO standard	Outlet pressure is between 2 and 2.5 bar	
6	X	CO standard	Inlet pressure not less than 20 psi, note pressure	44 bar / 44 bar at end of flight
<u>Flows</u>				
7	X	Ozone sample flows	Flow ~ 07. LPM on both channels	
8	X	NOx sample flow	~ 1 LPM	
9	X	NOx Ozonator flow	~ 0.065 LPM	
10	X	CO lamp flow	~ 40 ml/min	
11	X	CO pressure cell	~ 7.5 bar	
12	X	CO pressure monochromator	~ 5 bar	CO time sync @ 09:53:44
<u>Zeros</u>				
13	X	Ozone zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
14	X	NOx zero	Performed OK (if not approx zero note values)	
15	X	CO zero	Left for approx 10 min	10:20:13 – 11:00:06
16	X	SO ₂ zero (not for most flights)	Left for approx 10 min	
<u>Other</u>				
17	X	Tubing	All inlets / exhausts connected	
18	X	HORACE data	Check data is being displayed and recorded	
19	No	CO calibration	If unattended set to auto cal (40 min)	
<u>TDLAS</u>				
20	n/a	230V	230V power breakers on	
21	n/a	28V	Red LED on front panel (ensure LTI breaker on)	
22	n/a	Laptop	On and software working	
23	n/a	Data	Being saved to correct directories	

Post flight

<u>Switch Off</u>				
1	X	CO	Switch off instrument	
2	X	Ozone	Switch off monitor	
3	X	NOx	Switch off monitor	
4	X	Pumps	Switch off all pumps	
5	X	Breaker	Pop all breakers on rack and SSP	
<u>Gases (note pressures)</u>				
6	X	CO ₂ /Ar	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	See above
7	X	CO standard	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi	See above
8	X	Nitrogen	Close valves and check inlet pressure not below 20 psi If below 20 psi then the cylinder needs changing refilling	See above, couldn't refill post flight as gas cylinder unavailable
<u>Driers</u>				
9	X	Small drier	Change if spent	
10	X	Large drier	Change if spent	
<u>TDLAS</u>				
11	n/a	Data transfer	To memory stick	
12	n/a	Laptop	Shut down	
13	n/a	Switch off instrument	Pull all breakers IF no other instrument on	
<u>Log</u>				
14	X	Flight Log	Put log in folder (notify Ruth of any issues)	
15	None	Faults	Fill out separate log for in flight issues put in flight folder	
16	n/a	TDLAS data	Send to project spaces on BADC	

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 418

Date: 10/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 1 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
11:32:40																40 microns into CDP	
11:38:46																Start Profile 1 from takeoff	
12:02:25	300	0.07	3													End of Profile 1 @ FL060	
12:03:27	230	0.07														Start Profile 2 from FL060	
12:04:26	30	0.07														FL050	
12:05:26	1200	0.07	95													FL040	
12:06:23	1000	0.07														FL030	
12:07:23	915	0.07														FL020	
12:09:25	1190	0.07														FL010	
12:10:38																End of Profile 2 & Start Profile 3 @ 50'	
12:11:00	1130	0.07	96													End of Profile 3 & Start Run 1@ 500'	
12:13:00	1090	0.07															
12:15:00	1050	0.07															
12:17:00	1080	0.07															
12:19:00	1140	0.07															
12:20:40																End of Run 1 & Start Profile 4	
12:21:21	1050	0.07														FL010	
12:22:20	1250	0.07														FL020	
12:22:48																End of Profile 4 & Start Run @ 2500'	
12:23:00	1050	0.07															
12:25:00	900	0.07															
12:27:00	860	0.07	97														
12:29:00	900	0.07															
12:31:00	900	0.07															
12:33:00	950	0.07															
12:33:44																End of Run & Start Profile 5	
12:35:25																End of Profile 5 & Start Run 3 @ 3700'	
12:36:00	600	0.20	345			7	100	450	15			0.5	250	15	0.4	12	
12:38:00	800	0.20	610			8	150	360	15			0.5	250	16	0.4	1	
12:40:00	900	0.20	1066			20	150	600	15			0.5	260	15	0.45	1	
12:42:00	560	0.21	1415			15	175	500	14			0.3	250	14	0.4	1	
12:44:00	670	0.19	1778			10	250	490	15			0.3	250	15	0.4	1	
12:45:27																End of Run 3 & Start Profile 6	
12:46:06	30	0.07														End of Profile 6 & Start Profile 7 from 4900'	
12:46:30	220	0.13	2133			6	100	600	15			0.6	300	16	0.6	12	
12:47:39	440	0.09	2314			8	250									FL040	
12:48:0	1100	0.07														FL030	
12:49:50	930	0.07	2315													FL020	
12:50:49	800	0.07														FL010	
12:51:00	800	0.07														End of Profile 7 & Start Run 4 @ 500'	
12:53:00	800	0.07															
12:55:00	800	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 418

Date: 10/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 2 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
12:57:00	890	0.07	2315														
12:59:00	1200	0.07	2316														
13:00:49																End of Run 4 & Start Profile 8	
13:01:32	1050	0.07														FL010	
13:02:35	900	0.07														FL020	
13:04:36																End of P8 & Start Run 5 @ FL034	
13:05:00	1100	0.19	2744			15	200	400	17			0.6	200	20	0.8	1	
13:07:00	950	0.19	3098			20	200	460	17			0.35	250	18	0.6	1	
13:09:00	680	0.12	3333			6	125	430	17			0.1	250	16	0.4	1	
13:11:00	670	0.18	3801			20	100	450	16			0.1	250	13	0.25	12	
13:13:00	640	0.21	4105			10	100	450	15			0.1	250	14	0.3	12	
13:16:18																End of Run & Start Profile 10	
13:18:05																End of Profile 10 & Start Run 6	
13:22:00	70	0.07	4737														
13:24:00	70	0.07	4738														
13:26:00	60	0.07															
13:28:00	60	0.07															
13:30:04																End of Run 6 & Start Profile 11	
13:30:58	80	0.07														FL040	
13:31:55	130	0.09	4829			3	150								1	FL030	
13:32:58	800	0.08														FL020	
13:33:52	700	0.07														FL010	
13:36:14	1000	0.07														End of Profile 11 @ 50'	
13:36:58	870	0.07														Start Run 7 @ 500'	
13:37:00	850	0.07															
13:39:00	680	0.07															
13:41:00	635	0.07															
13:43:00	810	0.07															
13:45:00	680	0.07															
13:46:57																End of Run 7 & Start Profile 12	
13:47:36	500	0.07	4830													FL010	
13:48:36	430	0.07														FL020	
13:50:43																End of Profile 12 & Start Run 8 @ 3500'	
13:51:00	510	0.20	5142			20	200	380	16			0.3	200	19	0.6	1	
13:53:00	660	0.19	5403			35	200	300	17			0.2	150	20	0.4	1	
13:55:00	580	0.18	5647			45	200	300	17			0.3	175	20	0.6	1	
13:57:00	540	0.20	5947			60	150	150	18			0.1	160	18	0.4	1	
13:59:00	600	0.18	6187			35	200	350	18			0.2	200	20	0.6	1	
14:00:44																End of Run 8 & Start Profile 12.1	
14:01:16	40	0.07														End of P 12.2 & Start P14 @ 4500'	
14:02:20	220	0.09	6467			10	200	350	18			0.2	200	18	0.4	1	
14:04:10	450	0.07														FL010	
14:06:21	560	0.07														End of Profile 12.2	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 418

Date: 10/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 3 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
14:06:55			6500													Start Run 9 @ 500'	
14:07:00	440	0.07															
14:09:00	470	0.07															
14:11:00	400	0.07															
14:13:00	410	0.07															
14:15:00	470	0.07	6503														
14:17:00	470	0.07															
14:19:00	540	0.07															
14:21:00	560	0.07															
14:23:00	520	0.07															
14:25:00	650	0.07															
14:27:00	650	0.07															
14:29:00	700	0.07	6504														
14:31:00	800	0.07															
14:33:00	840	0.07	6505			1	250								1		
14:35:00	1100	0.07															
14:37:00	1150	0.07															
14:39:00	1130	0.07															
14:41:00	1150	0.07															
14:43:00	1100	0.07	6506														
14:45:00	1050	0.07															
14:47:00	1100	0.07															
14:49:00	1150	0.07															
14:51:00	1000	0.07															
14:53:00	920	0.07															
14:55:00	950	0.07															
14:57:00	820	0.07															
14:59:00	780	0.07															
15:01:00	760	0.07															
15:04:49																End of Run 9 & Start Profile 13	
15:05:22	1020	0.07	6508													FL010	
15:06:12	1250	0.07														FL020	
15:07:06	1180	0.07														FL030	
15:08:42																End of Profile & Start Run 10 @	
15:09:00	380	0.12	6746			12	100	500	13			0.2	250	15	0.3	12	
15:11:00	420	0.17	7642			20	125	460	13			0.3	210	15	0.3	12	
15:13:00	300	0.13	14828			30	125	300	14			0.25	200	14	0.2	12	
15:15:00	680	0.13	18508			50	150	320	16			0.65	220	20	0.8	12	
15:17:00	900	0.15	19772			30	200	460	17			0.7	250	20	0.8	1	
15:19:00	900	0.15	19131			70	175	800	18			0.9	320	20	1.0	1	
15:21:00	500	0.14	19349			30	225	250	16			0.4	200	18	0.4	1	
15:23:00	580	0.12	19654			70	225	270	18								
15:23:46																End of Run 10 & Start P14.1	

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 418

Date: 10/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 4 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
15:24:39	250	0.07														End of P14.1 & Start P14.2 from 4500'	
15:25:59	645	0.09	19817			5	250									FL030	
15:27:31	1100	0.07														End of P14.2 & Start P14.3	
15:28:28	900	0.07	19844													FL020	
15:30:17																End of P14.3 & Start Run 11 @ 3700'	
15:31:00	530	0.15	19960			40	200	500	15			0.7	200	20	0.6	1	
15:33:00	540	0.14	20240			100	200	200	20			0.4	180	19	0.3	1	
15:35:00	300	0.16	20441			50	200	340	17			0.35	200	15	0.3	1	
15:37:00	360	0.14	20651			40	100	280	15			0.4	200	0.3	15	1	
15:39:00	650	0.13	20910			10	100	300	19			0.4	200	20	0.45	1	
15:41:00	600	0.13	21210			20	125	300	18			0.5	200	20	0.6	1	
15:43:00	580	0.16	21425			35	100	350	18			0.5	200	20	0.4	1	
15:45:10																End of Run 11	
15:46:13																Start P15.1	
15:46:30	70	0.16														End of P15.1 & Start P15.2 @ 4000'	
15:47:35	310	0.11	21853													FL030	
15:48:40	860	0.07	21860													FL020	
15:49:16	800	0.07														End of P15.2 & Start P15.3	
15:49:58	850	0.07	21868													FL020	
15:51:00	680	0.07	21883													FL030	
15:51:20																End of P15.3 & Start Run 12 @ FL033	
15:52:00	440	0.10	21983			10	100	330	15			0.2	200	10	0.2	12	
15:54:00	320	0.08	22140			4	150	480	12			0.15	200	10	0.1	1	
15:55:39			FAIL													End of Run 12	
17:53:19																Start Run 13 @ FL060	
17:54:00	50	0.08	2														
17:56:00	55	0.07															
17:58:00	40	0.07															
18:00:00	30	0.07															
18:02:00	50	0.07															
18:04:00	100	0.07															
18:06:00	60	0.07															
18:11:02	60	0.07	3													End of Run 13 & Start Profile 16	
18:11:51	65	0.07														FL050	
18:12:39	430	0.11	41			47	175	220	20			0.8	80	15		FL040	
18:16:10	1000	0.07	135													FL010	
18:18:02	1150	0.07														End of P16 @ 50'	
18:18:38																Start Run 14 @ 500'	
18:19:00	1080	0.07															
18:21:00	980	0.07															
18:23:00	850	0.07															
18:25:00	830	0.07	136														
18:27:00	850	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 418

Date: 10/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 5 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
18:29:04																End of Run 14 & Start P17	
18:29:45	720	0.07	136													FL010	
18:30:51	740	0.07														FL020	
18:31:58	730	0.07	141			5	250	500	10			0.4	200	12	0.25	1	FL030
18:33:10	35	0.07															End of P17 & Start P18 from 4000'
18:34:14																	End of P18 & Start Run 15 @ 3500'
18:35:00	160	0.11	325			9	125	400	12			0.25	200	12	0.2	1	
18:37:00	310	0.13	587			20	100	240	15			0.7	250	15	0.6	12	
18:39:00	170	0.09	886			6	75	600	12			0.25	300	10	0.2	12	
18:41:00	720	0.07	1147			1		450	12			0.2	300	15	0.2		
18:43:00	270	0.11				6	50	400	12			0.2	250	12	0.2	12	
18:44:22																	End of Run & Start P19
18:45:02	900	0.07	1563														FL030
18:45:54	950	0.07	1568														FL020
18:46:47	1190	0.07	1569														FL010
18:47:45																	End of P19 & Start Run 16 @ 500'
18:49:00	1100	0.07															
18:51:00	1145	0.07															
18:53:00	1150	0.07															
18:55:00	1050	0.07															
18:57:00	1050	0.07															
18:57:50																	End of Run & Start Profile 20
18:58:30	900	0.07	1570														FL010
18:59:32	750	0.07															FL020
19:00:39	840	0.07	1571														FL030
19:01:49	70	0.07															End of P20 & Start P21 @ 4200'
19:02:44																	End of P21 & Start Run 17 @ 3600'
19:04:00	210	0.10	1802			1		500	11			0.3	200	11	0.2		
19:06:00	300	0.11	1995			2	100	600	12			0.25	220	13	0.2	12	
19:08:00	130	0.12	2325			3	75	500	11			0.2	220	12	0.2	12	
19:10:00	300	0.12	2557			7	75	400	12			0.3	200	12	0.2	12	
19:12:38																	End of Run & Start Profile 22
19:13:14	800	0.08	3018														FL030
19:14:09	1000	0.07	3023														FL020
19:15:14	1140	0.07															FL010
19:16:26																	End of P22 & Start Run 18 @ 500'
19:17:00	1065	0.07															
19:19:00	1050	0.07	3024														
19:21:00	980	0.07															
19:23:00	955	0.07															
19:25:00	900	0.07															
19:26:30																	End of Run 18 & Start P23
19:27:10	840	0.07															FL010

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG Flight B 418

Date: 10/11/08	Operator: MAP	DRS Time: 08:00:00	DAU1 Time: +0	DAU2 Time: +0	DAU3 Time: +0	Aux1 Time: +0	Aux2 Time: +0	Page 6 of 7
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G.M.T	PCASP		FFSSP	SID1	SID2	2D2-C		Manchester FSSP		CIP25			CDP			Habit	Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block TX	Count	Count	Conc/L	Max size	Conc/m3	Mean Dia	Conc m3	Max size	LWC	Conc m3	Mean Dia	LWC		
19:28:01	700	0.07														FL020	
19:29:00	630	0.07														FL030	
19:30:07	45	0.07	3082													End of Profile 23 & Start P24 FL040	
19:31:12																End of Profile 24 & Start Run 19 @ 3500'	
19:32:00	100	0.13	3177					440	12			0.2	200	12	0.18		
19:34:00	170	0.16	3450			1		500	12			0.3	200	14	0.2	12	
19:36:00	200	0.16	3834			1	75	300	13			0.25	250	14	0.2	12	
19:38:00	800	0.07															
19:39:53																End of Run & Start P25	
19:42:08	10	0.07														End of P25 & Start P26 @ 5000'	
19:43:05	30	0.07														FL040	
19:44:08	1550	0.07	3886													FL030	
19:45:06	1400	0.07														FL020	
19:46:23	1330	0.07	3887													FL010	
19:47:43																End of P26 & Start Run 20.1 @ 500'	
19:48:00	1430	0.07															
19:50:00	1500	0.07															
19:52:00	1850	0.07															
19:54:00	2300	0.07															
19:56:00	1800	0.07															
19:58:00	1700	0.07															
20:00:00	1400	0.07															
20:02:00	1300	0.07															
20:04:00	1250	0.07															
20:06:00	1100	0.07															
20:08:00	1000	0.07															
20:10:00	900	0.07															
20:12:00	700	0.07	3889														
20:12:27																End of Run 20.1	
20:13:22																Start Run 20.2 @ 500'	
20:14:00	870	0.07															
20:16:00	960	0.07															
20:18:00	900	0.07															
20:20:00	950	0.07															
20:22:00	1050	0.07															
20:24:00	1050	0.07															
20:26:00	1080	0.07															
20:28:00	980	0.07															
20:30:00	1030	0.07															
20:30:48																End of Run 20.2	
20:31:51																Start Run 20.3 @ 500'	
20:32:00	1020	0.07															
20:34:00	1020	0.07															

PCASP Reference Volts = 8V	FFSSP Reference Volts = 3.3V	2D2-C End element 1 voltage = -1.9V	CIP25 End element 1 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 1 voltage = n/a
PCASP Flow rate = 1.2CC/sec		2D2-C End element 32 voltage = -2.2V	CIP25 End element 64 voltage = 0.7V	CIP100 End element 64 voltage = n/a
© Met Office 2007	SID2 Laser power = n/a	2D2-P End element 1 voltage = n/a		

Flight No: B418

Date: 10/11/2008

Operator:JB

Type of filters mounted in			Upper inlet:				Lower inlet:	
Disk No 1 (top)	Disk No 2 (middle)	Disk No 3 (bottom)	Inlet <u>U</u> pper/ <u>L</u> ower	Time Pump On	Time Pump Off	Run	Accum Vol [l]	Comments eg. Filter Exposure No, period in cloud, change of level etc.
3	4	83	u	12:12	12:33	r1+r2	1290	counter reset
"	"	"	u	12:53	13:01	r3	449	
10	69	117	u	13:39	13:47	r7	519	
7	8	49	u	14:10	14:53	r9	2776	p2 to p3 run 500ft
								14:53 pump stopped for drizzle. counter not reset
"	"	"	u	14:55	15:05	r9	3371	
								Flight No.2
33	40	152	l	19:25	19:26	r18	111	Blank delay as inlet wet
"	"	"						not blank any more, exposed by mistake. Use both incase of water contamination. counter reset.
"	"	"		19:54	20:49	r20.1 r20.2 r20.3	3286	
1	2	no	u	19:23	19:26	r18	177	counter reset

		mark						
"	"	"		19:54	20:49	r20.1 r20.2 r20.3	3110	

Size	#	charged	FLIGHT/DATE	DISCHARGED	COMMENTS
10	1	9/11 HC	B418	11/11	
1	2	9/11 HC	10/11	HC	
10	3	9/11 HC	B418	11/11	
1	4	9/11 HC	10/11	HC	
10	21	9/11 HC	B418	11/11	
1	23	9/11 HC	10/11	HC	
10	7	9/11 HC	B418	11/11	
1	8	9/11 HC	10/11	HC	
10	16	9/11 HC	B418	11/11	
1	69	9/11 HC	10/11	HC	
10	33	9/11 HC	B418	11/11	edge loose from
1	40	9/11 HC	10/11	HC	O ring may have leaked

Flight:

B418

KEY

 Not Fitted

 Fitted, Not Operated

 Duff Data

 Minor Problem

 OK

Thermometers

Cabin Temperature:

Heimann:

Deiced Temp:

Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

FWVS:

Buck CR2:

General Eastern:

Johnson Williams:

Nevzorov:

Total Water Probe:

Cameras

Downward Facing:

Forward Facing:

Rearward Facing:

Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

Cruciform GPS:

GIN Applanix:

INU Honeywell:

Radar Altimeter:

RVSM IAS:

RVSM Static Pressure:

XR5 GPS:

Misc Core

HORACE:

AMTG:

AVAPS:

Cabin Pressure:

Printer:

S9 Static Pressure:

Satcom C:

Satcom H (VIRC):

Turb Centre-Static:

Turb Left Right:

Turb Up-Down:

Turb Horizontal Chk:

Turb Vertical Chk:

Weather Radar:

DLUs:

DLU AERACK:

DLU BBR Lower:

DLU BBR Upper:

DLU Core Chem:

DLU Core Consoles:

DLU Port Aft:

DLU Port Fwd:

DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

BBR (clear) Lower:

BBR (IR) Lower:

BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

BBR (clear) Upper:

BBR (IR) Upper:

BBR (red) Upper:

ARIES:

DEIMOS:

IR Camera:

JNO2 Lower:

JNO2 Upper:

JO1D Lower:

JO1D Upper:

MARSS:

SHIMS Lower:

SHIMS Upper:

SWS:

TAFTS:

Cloud Probes

2DC:

2DP:

FFSSP:

PCASP:

PCASP SPP-200:

2DS:

ADA:

CAPS:

CCN:

CDP (fuselage):

CDP (Canister):

CIP 100 (PIP):

CIP 25 (CIP):

CPI:

CVI (Inlet):

CVI PCASP-X:

CVI Ly-A Hygro:

FSSP (UMan):

SID1:

SID2:

SID3:

Aerosol

CPC 3025A:

CPC 3786 H2O:

Filters 47mm:

Filters 90mm:

Neph - Dry:

Neph - Wet:

PSAP:

AMS:

CPC (AMS):

SMPS (AMS):

CPC 3010A (CVI):

INC:

Mini-LIDAR:

SP2:

UHSAS:

VACC:

Chemistry

CO Aerolaser 5002:

NOx TE42C:

Ozone TE49C:

Ozone TE49:

SO2 TE43C:

TDLAS (NIR) CH4:

TDLAS (NIR) CO2:

FAGE:

Formaldehyde:

NOx FAAM:

NOxy:

ORAC:

PAN:

PERCA:

Peroxide:

PTRMS:

TDLAS (1C):

WAS Bags:

WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

CASI/ATM:

LIDAR (big):

LTI:

SAW Hygrometer:

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B418

Date: 10/11/08

Issues

1. BBRs- Upper Pyrgeometer signal and zero very noisy.
2. RFC/DFC bay – suspect water running down inside of RFC window at 1225Z and DFC – 1243. Pictures okay but need to do visual check pre next flight.
3. Radalt – Signal dropped to 0 at 1435, reset PAFT CB then okay.
4. TWC – Detector signal occasionally topping out at 4095 around 1445Z onwards. Status bit 4094. Window needing cleaned?

Instruments

Dropsondes	Nil
CVI -	ok
Filters	ok
Neph	ok
PSAP	ok
WetNeph	ok
AMS	ok
Core Chem	ok
Cloud physics -	ok PCASP channel 1 noisy otherwise scale error (leak) Ok FFSSP one hard disc fallover - 1 minutes data loss at end
ARIES -	ok , no more data after 1946Z, run out of disk space
MARSS -	ok
SWS -	ok except for 2 10-minute drop outs
CCN	ok, single channel only. On 2 nd flight, SSN switched between 0.4 and 0.1 on zigzags
VACC -	Laser voltage 4V, VACC not working, needs mirrors cleaning
CPC	ok
PAN	ok
2DS -	ok
CAPS -	ok
SMPS -	ok
Buck -	experimental operation ->ok

Aircraft

SatcomC	weather data not received, other ops normal
MPDS	Run for flight, ok
ISDN Emails	Nil
Satcom-H Calls	Nil

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 7/11/8

Flight No: B 418

Pre-Flighter: Gratton

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
1	☒	Hangar	Collect spanners for core chem	
<u>Aircraft Cabin: Power-up</u>				
2	☒	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	☒	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	☒	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
5	☒	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	
6	☒	Aft CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
7	☒	Fore CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	Note: UPS output CB had pop out
8	☒	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
9	☒	HORACE	Recording data	
10	☒	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
11	☒	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
12	☒	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
13	☒	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
14	☒	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	☒	Video Laptop	Checked onboard	NOT PRESENT
16	☐	FWVS	Set up & check on AUTO	Cy. 1000
17	☒	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked then OFF	
18	☒	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
19	☒	TWC	Fitted & signals checked	
20	☒	GE	Balance checked then back to DP	
21	☒	GPS (XR5M)	Checked	
22	☒	Satcom C	Checked	
23	☒	Video x 2	Records okay, -Rewind	

No.	✓ or x	Location	Action	Comments
24	☒	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	In cockpit
25	☐	CNC	Butanol filled	Left to operator
26	☐	Dry Neph	Power up & Zero Cal	Left to operator
27	☐	PSAP	Pre-flight log actions complete	
28	☐	CGPS	CBs and PC ON	Not fitted
<u>External Checks</u>				
29	☒	Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	☒	JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	☒	DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	☒	NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	☒	Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	☒	GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	☒	Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	☒	Camera Windows	Cleaned	
37	☒	Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	☒	TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	☒	All other covers	Removed	
40	☒	Pre-flight Bag	Returned to hold	** Check no butanol**
41	☒	Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	☒	Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>				
44	☐	Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		Signed 3 days ago
45	☒	ICEX applied		
46	☒	Turb Probe - Traps emptied, detail contents -	a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) 1/4 full or more	W. H. G.
47	☒	Turb Probe - Traps dried and resealed		

CVI log

11/10/08 9:37:58 AM pcasp talking ok
11/10/08 9:38:01 AM horace ok
11/10/08 9:38:04 AM cpc ok
11/10/08 9:38:09 AM lyman still off
11/10/08 9:38:21 AM counterflow on to dry out the system
11/10/08 9:40:32 AM
11/10/08 10:58:22 AM
11/10/08 11:00:03 AM new lyman zero, dillution up to one half
11/10/08 11:02:48 AM counterflow off to check the data stream on cpc and pcasp
11/10/08 11:05:01 AM data present noise pcasp1 very high cpc
11/10/08 11:05:44 AM data present noise pcasp1 very high cpc
11/10/08 11:11:00 AM back to counterflow mode
11/10/08 11:39:10 AM in flight nocloud to pass through
11/10/08 11:41:04 AM new lyman zero
11/10/08 11:47:03 AM above cloud boundary now
11/10/08 11:54:22 AM above cloud boundary now
11/10/08 11:54:39 AM above cloud boundary now
11/10/08 11:55:04 AM expecting smaller droplet sizes today, so set L control to a bit lower than yesterday, start using 1.8
11/10/08 11:57:07 AM leave the ams, cpi, inc flows set up as in cloud for the whole flight
11/10/08 11:58:05 AM fall in cpc
11/10/08 11:58:26 AM fall in cpc
11/10/08 11:58:28 AM fall in cpc
11/10/08 11:58:53 AM fall in cpc
11/10/08 11:58:58 AM fall in cpc
11/10/08 11:59:03 AM fall in cpc
11/10/08 12:01:10 PM fall in cpc
11/10/08 12:04:12 PM lyman to reference air for cloud
11/10/08 12:05:28 PM and ly to sample
11/10/08 12:23:20 PM and ly to sample
11/10/08 12:23:25 PM and ly to sample
11/10/08 12:23:45 PM and ly to sample
11/10/08 12:23:49 PM and ly to sample
11/10/08 12:26:37 PM and ly to sample
11/10/08 12:29:17 PM does the lyman alpha show signs of decouple layerd boundary
11/10/08 12:29:54 PM remove the bit of code that enters the text string EVERY time the enter key is pressed!
11/10/08 12:29:55 PM remove the bit of code that enters the text string EVERY time the enter key is pressed!
11/10/08 12:29:56 PM remove the bit of code that enters the text string EVERY time the enter key is pressed!
11/10/08 12:34:36 PM INTO CVI MODE
11/10/08 12:34:57 PM WILL TAKE SOME TIME FLOR FLORWS TO BALANCE
11/10/08 12:35:07 PM
11/10/08 12:35:30 PM
11/10/08 12:35:34 PM
11/10/08 12:35:40 PM
11/10/08 12:35:44 PM
11/10/08 12:36:11 PM
11/10/08 12:36:16 PM
11/10/08 12:36:29 PM
11/10/08 12:36:50 PM tip a bit warm, counterflow reading a bit warm
11/10/08 12:37:55 PM tip a bit warm, counterflow reading a bit warm
11/10/08 12:37:58 PM tip a bit warm, counterflow reading a bit warm
11/10/08 12:42:49 PM tip a bit warm, counterflow reading a bit warm
11/10/08 12:42:54 PM tip a bit warm, counterflow reading a bit warm
11/10/08 12:45:50 PM tip a bit warm, counterflow reading a bit warm
11/10/08 12:46:03 PM leave in cf for clud passage, removed the ams
11/10/08 12:47:52 PM cloud base into aerosol
11/10/08 12:50:18 PM cloud base into aerosol
11/10/08 12:50:22 PM cloud base into aerosol
11/10/08 12:56:14 PM cloud base into aerosol
11/10/08 12:58:18 PM there seem to be numerous step changes today as we head south.
11/10/08 12:58:44 PM both in the cloud run earlier, and in the aerosol measurements that we are seeing now

11/10/08 12:58:56 PM both in the cloud run earlier, and in the aerosol measurements that we are seeing now
11/10/08 12:59:00 PM both in the cloud run earlier, and in the aerosol measurements that we are seeing now
11/10/08 1:02:22 PM turn to counterflow mode
11/10/08 1:02:35 PM turn to counterflow mode
11/10/08 1:02:41 PM turn to counterflow mode
11/10/08 1:05:19 PM near CLOUD TOP
11/10/08 1:05:24 PM near CLOUD DORNIER NOW
11/10/08 1:06:24 PM cpc=600, pcasp=40, cwc=0.3
11/10/08 1:06:58 PM must be very near cloud top, as bright above
11/10/08 1:07:24 PM
11/10/08 1:07:31 PM
11/10/08 1:16:43 PM
11/10/08 1:16:50 PM ams off counterflow
11/10/08 1:18:43 PM into aerosol mode for above cloud sampling
11/10/08 1:28:30 PM into aerosol mode for above cloud sampling
11/10/08 1:28:36 PM into aerosol mode for above cloud sampling
11/10/08 1:28:39 PM into aerosol mode for above cloud sampling
11/10/08 1:28:44 PM into aerosol mode for above cloud sampling
11/10/08 1:29:15 PM counterflow for profile until below cloud
11/10/08 1:30:42 PM counterflow for profile until below cloud
11/10/08 1:31:08 PM l control to 2
11/10/08 1:31:10 PM in cloud
11/10/08 1:31:20 PM in cloud
11/10/08 1:31:25 PM in cloud
11/10/08 1:31:28 PM in cloud
11/10/08 1:32:30 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:32:56 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:35:21 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:35:25 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:35:28 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:39:20 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:39:23 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:39:27 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:39:29 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:39:38 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:39:43 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:39:47 PM below cloud back to aerosol
11/10/08 1:40:18 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:41:16 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:41:20 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:41:39 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:41:42 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:41:54 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:42:01 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:42:51 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:42:54 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:43:16 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:43:22 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:43:30 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:44:28 PM white caps, more sea salt, larger particles, some counts in higher sizes of pcasp
11/10/08 1:47:58 PM climbing - dial in ams flow
11/10/08 1:48:02 PM climbing - dial in ams flow
11/10/08 1:48:37 PM into counterflow - 1kft to go
11/10/08 1:48:43 PM ams onto cvi

11/10/08 1:48:53 PM ams onto cvi
11/10/08 1:49:25 PM ams onto cvi
11/10/08 1:49:28 PM ams onto cvi
11/10/08 1:49:32 PM ams onto cvi
11/10/08 1:49:41 PM ams onto cvi
11/10/08 1:49:45 PM ams onto cvi
11/10/08 1:50:58 PM ams onto cvi
11/10/08 1:51:06 PM ams onto cvi
11/10/08 1:52:48 PM cloud tops
11/10/08 1:53:45 PM cloud tops
11/10/08 1:53:52 PM cloud tops
11/10/08 1:54:43 PM cloud tops
11/10/08 1:54:48 PM cloud tops
11/10/08 1:57:47 PM cloud tops
11/10/08 1:57:51 PM cloud tops
11/10/08 1:57:54 PM cloud tops
11/10/08 2:03:18 PM below cloud into cvi, lyman to reference for a new zero
11/10/08 2:04:19 PM below cloud into cvi, lyman to reference for a new zero
11/10/08 2:04:29 PM below cloud into cvi, lyman to reference for a new zero
11/10/08 2:04:41 PM below cloud into cvi, lyman to reference for a new zero
11/10/08 2:04:46 PM below cloud into cvi, lyman to reference for a new zero
11/10/08 2:05:01 PM zero lyman
11/10/08 2:05:09 PM zero lyman
11/10/08 2:05:15 PM zero lyman
11/10/08 2:05:20 PM zero lyman
11/10/08 2:05:29 PM zero lyman
11/10/08 2:05:54 PM zero lyman again
11/10/08 2:06:13 PM lyman back to sample at 50ft
11/10/08 2:09:21 PM still lots of cloud, hint of decoupling with a layer below?
11/10/08 2:09:29 PM
11/10/08 2:09:32 PM
11/10/08 2:11:05 PM
11/10/08 2:11:09 PM
11/10/08 2:11:14 PM
11/10/08 2:11:17 PM
11/10/08 2:11:20 PM
11/10/08 2:11:27 PM
11/10/08 2:11:30 PM
11/10/08 2:11:45 PM big spike a minute ago? was that real?
11/10/08 2:13:13 PM check the plenu p
11/10/08 2:13:43 PM check the plenum pressure at the spike - it is not there on vacc
or cnc rack
11/10/08 2:15:24 PM
11/10/08 2:15:30 PM
11/10/08 2:17:12 PM
11/10/08 2:19:27 PM total water content reports 1.62g/m3
11/10/08 2:21:43 PM total water content reports 1.62g/m3, but lycww reports 8.0
11/10/08 2:22:44 PM total water content reports 1.62g/m3, but lycww reports 8.0
11/10/08 2:22:51 PM total water content reports 1.62g/m3, but lycww reports 8.0
11/10/08 2:24:37 PM total water content reports 1.62g/m3, but lycww reports 8.0
11/10/08 2:25:36 PM total water content reports 1.62g/m3, but lycww reports 8.0
11/10/08 2:27:06 PM total water content reports 1.62g/m3, but lycww reports 8.0
11/10/08 2:27:10 PM total water content reports 1.62g/m3, but lycww reports 8.0
11/10/08 2:27:31 PM need to get more range on the plots - cant see th whole of a long
run
11/10/08 2:27:41 PM
11/10/08 2:27:49 PM
11/10/08 2:30:45 PM
11/10/08 2:32:10 PM drizzle reported by cloud physics
11/10/08 2:32:18 PM must be getting drop shattering
11/10/08 2:32:24 PM cu below sc from ms1
11/10/08 2:32:34 PM cu below sc from ms1
11/10/08 2:32:37 PM cu below sc from ms1
11/10/08 2:32:42 PM cu below sc from ms1
11/10/08 2:34:22 PM cu below sc from ms1
11/10/08 2:34:25 PM cu below sc from ms1
11/10/08 2:34:32 PM cu below sc from ms1
11/10/08 2:34:35 PM cu below sc from ms1
11/10/08 2:35:07 PM cu below sc from ms1

11/10/08 2:36:08 PM strong dip in lycwc
11/10/08 2:36:14 PM strong dip in lycwc
11/10/08 2:36:32 PM ignore cpc when in drizzle
11/10/08 2:39:42 PM ask jim crawford if the twc systematically reads under other probes - does that very last bit of h2o stay joined?
11/10/08 2:40:45 PM write the log to an html file instead ? then can view it in a browser
11/10/08 2:43:11 PM could get a ratio of sub micron to super micron particles cf relative scattering of red blue stuff
11/10/08 2:45:40 PM cpc counts are falling off now
11/10/08 2:50:50 PM cpc counts are falling off now
11/10/08 2:50:53 PM cpc counts are falling off now
11/10/08 2:53:10 PM drizzle on the screen, spikes in cpc opc
11/10/08 2:53:57 PM the aircraft screen not the laptop
11/10/08 2:55:46 PM the aircraft screen not the laptop
11/10/08 2:55:50 PM the aircraft screen not the laptop
11/10/08 2:55:53 PM the aircraft screen not the laptop
11/10/08 2:55:57 PM the aircraft screen not the laptop
11/10/08 2:56:03 PM the aircraft screen not the laptop
11/10/08 2:56:08 PM the aircraft screen not the laptop
11/10/08 2:56:11 PM the aircraft screen not the laptop
11/10/08 2:56:27 PM main feature is the change of wind speen, now light and variable
11/10/08 2:57:19 PM spike at about 14:56 seems real - mirrored in the cnc rack
11/10/08 3:08:13 PM into cvi a bit late, ams on as well
11/10/08 3:09:02 PM run at 3.7kft
11/10/08 3:09:06 PM run at 3.7kft
11/10/08 3:09:09 PM run at 3.7kft
11/10/08 3:09:14 PM run at 3.7kft
11/10/08 3:10:30 PM run at 3.7kft
11/10/08 3:10:39 PM run at 3.7kft
11/10/08 3:10:43 PM run at 3.7kft
11/10/08 3:11:55 PM in cloud tops
11/10/08 3:14:00 PM in cloud tops
11/10/08 3:14:05 PM in cloud tops
11/10/08 3:25:25 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:32:30 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:33:50 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:33:53 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:33:57 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:36:06 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:36:10 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:36:21 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:36:25 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:36:27 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:39:46 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:39:56 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:40:03 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:40:08 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:41:26 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:41:36 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:41:52 PM lyman does not zero on the pop above cloud
11/10/08 3:50:29 PM in cloud
11/10/08 3:53:29 PM alter dilution factor
11/10/08 3:53:37 PM alter dilution factor
11/10/08 3:53:41 PM alter dilution factor
11/10/08 3:54:38 PM alter dilution factor
11/10/08 3:54:43 PM alter dilution factor
11/10/08 3:56:09 PM lyman to reference air
11/10/08 3:56:43 PM still a reasonable zero, lcwc=0.35 WITH ef OFF
11/10/08 3:57:03 PM end of science cf up high
11/10/08 3:57:32 PM pcasp had a good zero above cloud before increasing cf

CVI log

11/10/08 5:00:33 PM lyman i=0.6, i0=0.8 on start up - this should increase as the instrument warms up

11/10/08 5:01:39 PM i0=

11/10/08 5:01:41 PM i0=143

11/10/08 5:01:46 PM i0=145

11/10/08 5:02:03 PM i0=1.55

11/10/08 5:02:17 PM i0=1.60

11/10/08 5:02:51 PM i0=1.7

11/10/08 5:03:57 PM i0=1.8

11/10/08 5:07:45 PM stable at 1.87

11/10/08 5:08:15 PM zero lyman

11/10/08 5:09:01 PM noise in chn 2 pcasp

11/10/08 5:19:52 PM noise in chn 2 pcasp

11/10/08 5:19:57 PM noise in chn 2 pcasp

11/10/08 5:20:27 PM noise in chn 2 pcasp

11/10/08 5:20:29 PM noise in chn 2 pcasp

11/10/08 5:28:54 PM zero lyman alpha

11/10/08 5:29:35 PM noise on pcasp

11/10/08 5:54:44 PM counterflow off

11/10/08 5:55:56 PM counterflow off

11/10/08 5:55:59 PM counterflow off

11/10/08 5:56:58 PM counterflow off

11/10/08 5:57:02 PM counterflow off

11/10/08 5:57:18 PM counterflow off

11/10/08 5:58:24 PM very low concs cf previous - pcasp only 30cc-1

11/10/08 5:59:57 PM zero lyman and turn to sample

11/10/08 6:03:37 PM just abov cloud now

11/10/08 6:04:33 PM just abov cloud now

11/10/08 6:05:11 PM just abov cloud now

11/10/08 6:06:19 PM checking the zero

11/10/08 6:06:23 PM checking the zero

11/10/08 6:06:27 PM checking the zero

11/10/08 6:07:48 PM checking the zero

11/10/08 6:07:51 PM checking the zero

11/10/08 6:07:54 PM checking the zero

11/10/08 6:08:35 PM checking the zero

11/10/08 6:08:40 PM checking the zero

11/10/08 6:10:48 PM generally zero on the pcasp, but some particles are therrere

11/10/08 6:11:13 PM zero seems to be now 2.4, although we are at fl060

11/10/08 6:12:27 PM in cloud

11/10/08 6:12:52 PM in cloud

11/10/08 6:14:23 PM back into aerosol

11/10/08 6:15:59 PM still high on cpc - still drizzle

11/10/08 6:16:07 PM still high on cpc - still drizzle

11/10/08 6:16:29 PM more like cnc cpc now

11/10/08 6:27:55 PM more like cnc cpc now

11/10/08 6:28:00 PM more like cnc cpc now

11/10/08 6:31:01 PM into cvi with ams

11/10/08 6:31:12 PM hit the base of the cu before switching

11/10/08 6:31:21 PM hit the base of the cu before switching

11/10/08 6:31:25 PM hit the base of the cu before switching

11/10/08 6:32:27 PM counterflow must be too high

11/10/08 6:32:30 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:32:55 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:33:01 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:33:05 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:33:08 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:33:12 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:33:15 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:33:19 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:33:33 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:33:38 PM dropped to 2.2

11/10/08 6:34:19 PM nudge back down to 2

11/10/08 6:35:41 PM nudge back down to 2

11/10/08 6:37:30 PM nudge back down to 2

11/10/08 6:38:31 PM nudge back down to 2

11/10/08 6:38:37 PM nudge back down to 2

11/10/08 6:38:47 PM nudge back down to 2
11/10/08 6:38:52 PM nudge back down to 2
11/10/08 6:38:56 PM nudge back down to 2
11/10/08 6:40:54 PM broken cloud
11/10/08 6:41:17 PM back in cloud
11/10/08 6:45:29 PM b ack into aerosol mode
11/10/08 6:46:05 PM passing throught the cu layer - in aeroso mode - worse things
have happened at sea
11/10/08 6:46:48 PM
11/10/08 6:46:53 PM
11/10/08 6:49:50 PM white caps on waves
11/10/08 6:50:02 PM a few particles in higher size bins
11/10/08 6:51:08 PM put L back to 2.0 for next cloud run
11/10/08 6:58:42 PM into cvi with AMS
11/10/08 6:59:49 PM
11/10/08 7:01:25 PM some big particles on enter cloud
11/10/08 7:05:12 PM some big particles on enter cloud
11/10/08 7:05:17 PM some big particles on enter cloud
11/10/08 7:05:20 PM some big particles on enter cloud
11/10/08 7:05:30 PM some big particles on enter cloud
11/10/08 7:11:45 PM some big particles on enter cloud
11/10/08 7:11:50 PM some big particles on enter cloud
11/10/08 7:14:19 PM ams gone
11/10/08 7:14:22 PM ams gone
11/10/08 7:14:32 PM leave in counterflow to get any drizzle
11/10/08 7:16:18 PM back into aerosol mode
11/10/08 7:17:32 PM back into aerosol mode
11/10/08 7:17:40 PM
11/10/08 7:20:03 PM
11/10/08 7:25:19 PM
11/10/08 7:25:24 PM
11/10/08 7:29:05 PM switch to cvi
11/10/08 7:29:15 PM in cloud late switch
11/10/08 7:29:26 PM in cloud late switch
11/10/08 7:29:31 PM in cloud late switch
11/10/08 7:30:54 PM in cloud
11/10/08 7:35:09 PM in cloud
11/10/08 7:35:16 PM in cloud
11/10/08 7:35:21 PM in cloud
11/10/08 7:37:23 PM in cloud
11/10/08 7:37:32 PM coming to cloud edge
11/10/08 7:37:49 PM out of cloud at the edge
11/10/08 7:38:33 PM ams gone
11/10/08 7:39:35 PM climb to above inversion
11/10/08 7:40:09 PM into cvi mode
11/10/08 7:41:27 PM into cvi mode
11/10/08 7:42:43 PM into cvi mode
11/10/08 7:43:00 PM dry above bl
11/10/08 7:43:44 PM cumulus in the gap between cloud
11/10/08 7:45:01 PM into bl just previous
11/10/08 7:46:16 PM into bl just previous
11/10/08 7:46:29 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 7:53:00 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 7:53:06 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 7:58:22 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 7:58:27 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 8:07:58 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 8:08:01 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 8:11:00 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 8:11:31 PM very high pcasp counts
11/10/08 8:13:32 PM start run 20.2
11/10/08 8:13:48 PM should cross over the same plume a bit closer to home
11/10/08 8:13:59 PM concs climbing st
11/10/08 8:15:26 PM
11/10/08 8:15:31 PM
11/10/08 8:15:35 PM
11/10/08 8:28:06 PM lyman i0 is still 1.99 so good window cleaniliness
11/10/08 8:30:49 PM turning to head south to pick up the nose of the plume
11/10/08 8:53:27 PM lyman to reference

11/10/08 8:53:57 PM keep lyman off until landing
11/10/08 8:53:59 PM
11/10/08 8:54:46 PM end of science
11/10/08 8:56:08 PM counterflow on
11/10/08 9:22:54 PM last minute zero

ARIES flight log

Flight:

BCF18 A & B

page 1 of 1

Date: 10/Nov/2008

Operator(s): S. ROGERS

Res: 1

Gain A: 2 B: 2

Loc./Notes: VOCALS

Scans: either "[IGMs]X[co-adds]", or "[stop DRS time]" if in start/stop, or "[macro name]". View: mirror angle.

DRS time	Flt ptrn	Scans	View	Shtr	HBB	CBB	Comments
0945	On the ground.						Power On
101430			CH	C	71	31	ColdHotIn - script
103155	TAKE OFF FROM	ARICA					
104626	6000ft		O	NZ	71	31	NatZenLongRun 30sec End 1200
120224	pd						6000ft → 50ft.
120947	500ft		O	NZ	71	31	NatZenLongRun 30sec Banking
122040	↑		C				50ft to 2500
122155	2500ft		O	NZ	71	31	NatZenLongRun 30sec Below Sky Scr Hazy
123244	↑		C	-	71	31	—
124510	4400ft		O	Z			Zenith LongRun 3min - about 1/2 sec
124953	500ft		O	NZ	71	31	NatZenLongRun 30sec End ~1300
130404	3800ft		C	N	71	31	NatZenLongRun 3min In cloud
1310							Script lock up? - banking
131658	4900?		O	NZ	71	31	NatZenLongRun 3min End ~1330
1329	↓		C	-	71	31	- to 50ft
133540	500ft		O	NZ	71	31	NatZenLongRun 30sec End ~1346
13504	3500ft		C	CH	71	31	ColdHotIn In cloud.
130600	500ft		O	NZ	71	31	NatZenLongRun 30sec Banking.
							End ~1503 Climb to 3700ft
150955	3700ft		C	CH	71	31	ColdHotIn In cloud
155030	3500ft		C	CH	71	31	ColdHotIn —
~1614	LAND AT ANTOFAGASTA	FOR REFUELLING					No GPS - simulator off
~1750	TAKE OFF FROM ANTOFAGASTA						Time reset
1753	6000ft		O	Z	71	35	Zenith LongRun 3min
1807	"						Script lock-up - banking
180730	"		C	CH	71	35	ColdHotIn
181104	pd		C	-	71	35	6000ft to 50ft
181750			O	NZ	71	35	NatZenLongRun 30sec CBB slowly dropping
181830	500ft		C				→ end 1829
184422	↓ 3500ft		C		71	31	3500ft → 500ft
184820			O	NZ	71	31	NatZenLongRun 30sec. Operations halted due to pilot operator

NOTE: Time mismatch with Horace of about 1 minute Doh! (Horace ahead)

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	10/11/08	Flight	B418	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Campaign	VOCALS			
Departure						Arrival

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•
FERA on	at time					
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	18.2°C	Ch 17	18.0°C	Ch18	17.5°C
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C
MARSS CPU on	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot	289.0	Cold	287.4		
Target heating						•
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time					0945
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers						
Turn on Deimos CPU						
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						
Start Deimos Software	at time					
Initial target temperatures	Hot				Cold	
Target heating						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual		
Weather	Cloud	1/8 sc5	1/8 Ci1	Precip	Nil, again.	
	Surface			Pressure	1008	
	Other	Slight mist in places				

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot	Cold			
	Deimos:	Hot	Cold			
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

Flight #	B418	Date	10/11/08	Operator(s)	JNB	log page	2	of	4
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
1025			Start went really really really well. No problems. Marss pod shut down until needed.						
1100			MARSS pod back on. Take off will be start of science into P1↑ to FL060.						
113240	P1↑	0	Start of profile 1 below 1/8 Sc5 and 1/8 Ci1						
113846	P1↑	FL060	End of profile climb 1/8 Sc5 to starboard						
1146	-	FL060	Sc5 sheet now below will become 8/8 fairly rapidly						
1149	-	FL060	Sc5 actually 6/8 with a few POCS dotted around						
120224	P2↓	FL060	Start of profile descent to 50ft above 8/8 Sc5 below 1/8 Ac3 1/8 Ci1						
1204	!	!	Having difficulty with Horace. Do have flight summary open on Firefox but unable to get any other plots. Internet Explorer not working as usual.						
1205			Sc5 top at top at FL038						
1205			Cloud base approx FL032						
120924	P3↑	50ft	Start of profile climb to FL005						
121037	1	FL005	Start of run below 8/8 Sc5						
122040	P4↑	FL005	Start of profile climb to FL025 below 8/8 Sc5						
122247	2	FL025	Start of run below 7/8 Sc5						
123341	P5↑	FL025	Start of profile climb for in cloud run						
123524	3	FL038	Start of run in thin 7/8 Sc5						
124525	P6↑	FL038	Start of profile climb to FL044 above 7/8 Sc5 did not see any cloud above						
124623	P7↓	FL044	Start of profile decent to						
125047	4	FL005	Start of run below 7/8 Sc5						
130048	P8↑	FL005	Start of profile climb for in cloud run (into cloud at FL026)						
130435	5	FL038	Start of run in cloud at FL038						
130522	5	FL038	Dornier overpass						
131619	P9↑	FL038	Start of profile climb to FL049 to enable ease springs						
131805	6	FL049	Start of comfort run						
133002	P10↓	FL049	Start of profile descent to 50ft 1/8 of embedded Cu1 in Sc5 layer – believe it may have been there all along but difficult to spot. Would still call it Sc5 as opposed to Sc4						
1335	P10↓	?	Now below Sc5 and Cu1 far more noticeable						
133613	P10↓	50ft	End of profile						
133655	7	500ft	Start of run below 1/8 Cu1 7/8 Sc5						
134656	P11↑	500ft	Start of profile ascent below 7/8 Sc5 and 1/8 embedded Cu1						
135042	8	FL035	Start of in cloud run						
140042	P12↓	FL035	Start of profile descent to 50ft						
140620	P12.2↓	50ft	End of profile						
140655	9	FL005	Start of run no change in cloud amounts or type						
150449	P13↑	FL005	End of run with no significant change in cloud type or amount throughout. Climbing to FL036 for in cloud run						

Microwave Radiometers FLIGHT LOG		Date	10/11/08	Flight	B418b	log pages
Operator(s)	Jeff Norwood-Brown	Campaign	VOCALS			
Departure	Antofagasta	Arrival	Arica			

System start

MARSS

Visual pod inspection						•	
Close 3 SSP circuit breakers						•	
Close all MARSS circuit breakers						•	
FERA on	at time						
Temperature controller initial temps	Ch16	20.5°C	Ch 17	22.1°C	Ch18	20.8°C	
Temperature controller set points		54°C		58°C	-20	40°C	
MARSS CPU on	at time					1730	
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating						•	
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***						•	
Scanning on (LMD box)	at time						
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			•

Deimos

Close all Deimos circuit breakers							
Turn on Deimos CPU							
*** CHECK SCAN HEAD CLEAR ***							
Start Deimos Software	at time						
Initial target temperatures	Hot		Cold				
Target heating							
Scan indication	Monitor			Visual			
Weather	Cloud	1/8 Sc5		Precip	Nil		
	Surface	Pressure					
	Other						

System functionality check

(after initial system warmup, approx 1 hour)

PC to DRS Time error	$t_{PC}=t_{DRS} +$	0	at time			
Brightness temps 'sensible'						•
Target temps	MARSS:	Hot		Cold		
	Deimos:	Hot		Cold		
Channel gains 'sensible'	Ch1 A	Ch3 A	Ch1 B	Ch3 B		
	(-)	(-)	(-)	(-)		
	Ch16	Ch17	Ch18	Ch19	Ch20	
	(40-44)	(45-49)	(40-44)	(40-44)	(44-48)	

Power changeover

Headset on before start						•
Listen to engine start sequence	4, 3, 2, 1.					•
LMD off (3 switches, bottom to top)						•
Exit Deimos Software (x)						
POWER CHANGEOVER						
LMD on (3 switches, top to bottom)	then pushbutton					•
Restart Deimos Software						
System running again	at time					

Flight #	B418b	Date	10/11/08	Operator(s)	JNB	log page	2	of	3
Time	Run id	Alt/FL	Remarks				Sys		
1740			Start up ok if rushed – missed a few initial temperatures. Appols.						
			Profile started at T/O						
175316	13	FL060	Start of run above 2/8 Sc5/Cu1 1/8 Ci1 above						
1758	!	!	Will need to replace kick plate Velcro as they all fall off pretty much every T/O and Landing						
1802	13	FL060	Sc5 increased to 4/8						
1804	13	FL060	Sc5 increased to 7/8 no real evidence of embedded Cu but difficult to tell as Cu tops not getting through the strong inversion						
1810	13	FL060	Banking						
181104	13	FL060	Start of profile descent to 50ft. Above 8/8 Sc5 below 1/8 Ci						
181240	P16↓	FL042	Entering 8/8 Sc5 tops						
181804	P16↓	50ft	End of profile						
181838	14	FL005	Start of run. 1/8 Cu1 below 8/8 Sc5. Cu1 is not reaching Sc5 base.						
182908	P17↑	FL005	Start of profile climb						
1831	P17↑	FL022	Cu base at approx FL022						
183309	P18↓	FL043	Sc5 top at FL042						
183414	15	FL035	Start of run in cloud						
184422	P19↓	FL035	Profile descent to FL005						
1846	P19↓	FL035	2/8 Cu1 with 8/8 Sc5 above						
184745	16	FL005	Start of below cloud run						
1851	16	FL005	Sc5 now 7/8						
1853	16	FL005	Sc5 now 6/8						
185752	P20↑	FL005	Start of profile climb to FL045 2/8 Cu1 with 6/8 Sc5 above that						
190147	P21↓	FL045	Start of descent into 6/8 Sc5 at FL036						
190237	17	FL036	Start of in cloud run. Descended to FL035 to try and stay within clouds						
191240	P22↓	FL035	Profile descent to FL005						
191624	18	FL005	Start of run below 2/8 Cu1 which is below 7/8 Sc5. Precip around but unsure if we've been through any. Light rain/drizzle combined.						
192631	P23↑	FL005	Start of profile ascent to no sig change in cloud amounts or type						
193004	P24↓	FL042	Start of descent to FL035 above 7/8 Sc5 and below 1/8 Ci1. Sc5 cloud top FL037.						
193115	19	FL035	Start of in cloud run						
1934	19	FL034	Descended 100ft to remain in 7/8 Sc5						
1937	19	FL034	Struggling to reamain in cloud – constantly popping out the top						
1938	19	FL034	Have reached the edge of the Sc5 layer so Sc5 rapidly becoming nil and no Cu1 either.1/8 Ci1 remains						
193951	P25↑	FL034	Profile climb to FL048 vis over 10K nil cloud above or below us						
194217	P26↓	FL048	Profile descent to FL005 with no change in vis1/8 CuSc below						

B418_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

09:36:23.55 --- - - - -
09:36:23.55 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
09:36:23.55 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
09:36:23.55 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B418
09:36:23.55 --- - - - -
09:36:31.71 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
09:36:34.90 SWS -0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
09:36:35.45 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
09:36:40.57 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:36:42.39 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:36:47.99 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:36:51.90 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:36:53.28 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:36:55.22 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
09:36:57.84 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
09:37:00.81 USH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:37:03.06 LSH - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
09:37:08.03 SWS - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:37:08.03 SWS - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:37:11.67 USH - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:37:11.68 USH - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:37:14.97 LSH - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:37:14.97 LSH - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:37:22.63 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:37:22.63 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:37:22.63 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:37:43.67 LSH - - - - Idling
09:37:43.67 SWS - - - - Idling
09:37:43.73 USH - - - - Idling
09:37:45.67 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:37:50.82 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
09:37:55.25 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:37:55.26 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:37:55.26 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:37:55.78 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:37:56.69 SWS - - - - Idling
09:37:56.90 LSH - - - - Idling
09:37:57.09 USH - - - - Idling
09:38:02.29 LSH - - 5 - - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 5ms.
09:38:02.30 LSH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 5ms.
09:38:06.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:38:09.09 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:38:09.32 LSH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:38:09.58 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:38:14.28 LSH - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:38:14.29 LSH - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
09:38:18.22 LSH - - - - Idling
09:44:58.24 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:45:01.29 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:45:05.18 SWS - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
09:45:05.19 SWS - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
09:45:11.75 USH - - 600 - - VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
09:45:11.76 USH - - - 600 - - NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 600ms.
09:45:17.21 USH - - 300 - - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 300ms.
09:45:17.21 USH - - - 300 - - NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 300ms.
09:45:20.99 USH - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
09:45:21.00 USH - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 300ms to 100ms.
09:45:25.48 SWS - - 100 - - VIS int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
09:45:25.49 SWS - - - 100 - - NIR int.time changed from 600ms to 100ms.
09:45:29.46 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:45:30.90 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:45:31.56 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
09:45:33.00 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
09:45:35.95 SWS - - - - Idling
09:45:35.97 USH - - - - Idling
09:52:32.80 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.

```

09:52:45.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:52:46.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:52:51.26	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
09:52:52.92	SWS	170.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:53:00.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:53:09.28	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
09:53:10.40	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
09:54:15.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** 19 deg
09:58:34.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 18 deg
09:59:35.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:35.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:35.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:37.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:37.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:37.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:38.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
09:59:39.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:39.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:39.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:39.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:42.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:44.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
09:59:45.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
09:59:46.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:46.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
09:59:46.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:01:05.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:01:14.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:01:16.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:01:17.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:02:07.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
10:02:41.56	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
10:02:42.68	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
10:02:44.45	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:02:48.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:49.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:02:50.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:02:51.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:02:52.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:04:00.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
10:06:24.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
10:11:57.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:12:23.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:23.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:23.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:30.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:30.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:30.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:31.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:31.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:32.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:32.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:33.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:41.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:41.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:41.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:12:42.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:42.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:12:43.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:12:43.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:03.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:03.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:03.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:04.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:04.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:04.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:07.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:07.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:13:07.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:13:08.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:09.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:13:09.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:16:50.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
10:17:03.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:03.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:03.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:08.98	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:17:19.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:21.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:23.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:24.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:30.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:31.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:38.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:38.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:38.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:39.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:40.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:40.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:43.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:43.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:43.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:45.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:45.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:45.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:49.07	SWS	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:17:49.08	SWS	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:17:53.03	USH	-	-	40	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:17:53.04	USH	-	-	-	40	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 40ms.
10:17:55.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:55.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:55.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:55.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:56.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:17:56.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:56.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:57.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:17:59.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:17:59.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:01.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:01.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:01.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:02.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:02.86	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:03.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:04.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:04.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:04.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:18:05.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:05.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:05.81	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:18:10.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:10.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:10.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:18:16.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
10:18:53.83	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
10:22:58.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:22:58.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:22:58.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:06.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:07.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:07.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:08.63	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
10:23:15.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:15.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:15.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:17.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:17.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

10:23:17.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:18.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:19.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:19.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:19.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:24.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:23:25.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:23:28.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:28.69	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:23:28.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:03.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:03.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:03.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:06.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:06.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:06.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:07.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:07.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:08.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:27.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:27.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:27.28	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:56:28.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:28.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:28.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:56:32.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:32.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:56:32.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
10:59:18.02	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:18.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:18.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:37.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:37.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:37.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
10:59:38.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:39.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
10:59:39.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:13.55	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
11:00:14.68	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:00:23.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:23.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:23.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:00:24.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:25.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:00:25.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:57.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:57.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:57.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:05:58.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:58.67	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:05:58.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:00.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:00.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:00.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:01.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:06:01.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:01.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:06:02.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:06:05.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:35:16.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:35:42.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:37:53.59	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
11:37:59.80	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
11:38:00.92	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:38:02.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:02.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:02.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:03.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:03.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

11:38:04.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:05.48	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
11:38:11.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:11.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:11.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:38:12.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:12.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:13.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:38:21.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 11 deg
11:42:11.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
11:42:14.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
11:43:34.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:34.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:34.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:35.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:35.48	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:35.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:41.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:41.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:41.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:43:42.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:43.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:43:43.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:34.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear skies above and below
11:46:42.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:42.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:42.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:46:43.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:43.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:46:43.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:05.42	---	-	-	-	-	*** edge of stratq sheet
11:47:17.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** now over cloud
11:47:30.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:30.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:30.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:47:31.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:32.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:47:32.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:38.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:48:38.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:48:38.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:48:40.88	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
11:48:42.56	SWS	171.7	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
11:48:44.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:44.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:44.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:49.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:48:49.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:48:49.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:48:50.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:50.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:51.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:48:58.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
11:49:49.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:49:50.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:49:59.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:59.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:49:59.16	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:00.49	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:00.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:00.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:14.69	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
11:50:14.69	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
11:50:17.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:20.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:20.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:21.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:22.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:22.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

11:50:23.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
11:50:25.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:27.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:27.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:27.11	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
11:50:28.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:28.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:50:28.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
11:56:41.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
11:57:12.39	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:01:27.24	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:28.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:32.64	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:01:32.65	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 40ms to 30ms.
12:01:34.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:34.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:36.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:36.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:40.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:40.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:40.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:01:41.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:41.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:01:42.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:02:36.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 2
12:02:45.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending from FL 230
12:03:06.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
12:04:53.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3800 ft
12:05:35.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base 3200 ft
12:06:56.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 50 ft moving sws telescope to zenith
12:08:47.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
12:09:26.20	---	-	-	-	-	***
12:09:26.75	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:09:28.49	SWS	-5.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
12:09:40.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 3 climbing to 500 ft
12:09:46.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:46.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:46.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:09:47.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:47.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:09:48.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:10:42.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
12:10:47.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 1
12:13:36.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:36.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:36.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:13:37.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:37.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:13:38.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:16:18.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:20:44.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** endof run
12:20:51.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb 4
12:20:59.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** to 2500 ft
12:22:48.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
12:23:01.88	---	-	-	-	-	*** 2 at 2500 ft
12:23:07.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud run
12:23:35.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:25:38.07	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
12:27:19.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
12:33:43.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
12:33:46.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing
12:33:50.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:50.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:50.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:33:51.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:51.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:33:52.10	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:34:00.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** prfoile 5
12:34:27.35	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg

```

12:34:42.45 --- - - - - *** in cloud
12:35:25.25 --- - - - - *** end of profile
12:35:29.61 --- - - - - *** start of run
12:35:47.73 --- - - - - *** edging down to 3700 ft
12:35:58.21 --- - - - - *** run 3 at 3700 ft in cloud
12:38:33.81 --- - - - - *** 12 deg
12:38:58.46 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:38:59.27 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:02.60 LSH - - - - Idling
12:39:02.65 SWS - - - - Idling
12:39:02.66 USH - - - - Idling
12:39:04.45 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
12:39:07.69 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
12:39:10.94 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:10.94 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:10.97 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:11.50 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:11.70 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:12.64 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:12.74 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:12.76 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:13.61 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:13.86 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:14.14 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:46.83 --- - - - - *** SWS NIR just dropped out
12:39:49.90 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:50.72 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:52.96 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:52.97 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:53.03 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:39:53.75 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:54.27 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:39:54.73 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:40:46.69 --- - - - - *** going to try restarting software
12:40:50.74 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:40:50.80 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:40:50.84 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
12:40:51.50 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:40:51.75 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:40:52.59 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:42:08.17 --- - - - -
12:42:08.17 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
12:42:08.17 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
12:42:08.18 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B418
12:42:08.18 --- - - - -
12:42:12.10 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
12:42:14.84 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
12:42:16.24 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:42:18.95 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:42:21.98 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:50:02.40 --- - - - -
12:50:02.40 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
12:50:02.40 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
12:50:02.40 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B418
12:50:02.40 --- - - - -
12:50:07.25 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:50:15.11 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:50:19.00 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:50:20.12 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
12:50:21.29 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
12:50:24.79 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:50:24.79 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:50:24.81 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
12:50:26.44 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
12:50:29.04 SWS - - 30 - - - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
12:50:29.05 SWS - - - 30 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
12:50:31.06 USH - - - 5 - - - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.

```

12:50:32.93	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
12:50:32.93	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
12:50:35.40	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
12:50:38.11	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
12:50:38.12	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
12:50:52.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
12:50:55.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
12:50:58.30	SWS	-0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
12:51:17.03	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:51:21.72	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:21.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:21.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:51:22.69	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:22.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:51:23.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:54:06.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
12:58:22.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:22.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:22.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:22.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:58:22.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
12:58:22.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:23.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:23.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:26.10	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
12:58:30.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:30.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:30.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:30.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:31.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:31.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:33.37	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:33.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:33.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
12:58:34.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:34.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
12:58:35.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:00:50.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:01:17.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** was end of run 4 now on profile 8 and ascending
13:01:58.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
13:02:29.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** entering cloud
13:04:18.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile
13:04:36.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 3800 ft in cloud
13:04:40.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:40.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:40.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:41.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:04:41.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:04:41.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
13:04:41.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:41.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:42.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:45.73	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:04:49.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:50.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:50.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:50.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:50.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:51.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:53.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:53.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:53.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:04:54.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:54.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:04:55.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:05:13.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** underflying dornier around now
13:05:20.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:05:32.98	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000

13:05:34.71	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:07:09.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:08:04.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** easing down to 3700 ft to stay in cloud
13:09:16.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** going down to 3500 ft
13:12:04.61	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:04.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:04.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:05.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:05.60	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:06.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:16.05	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:12:17.73	SWS	-3.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:12:19.55	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:19.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:19.57	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:12:20.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:20.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:12:21.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:22.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
13:16:25.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
13:16:29.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
13:16:44.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:44.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:44.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:16:46.03	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:16:47.72	SWS	172.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:16:48.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:48.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:48.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:50.12	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:16:56.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:56.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:56.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:16:56.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:57.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:16:58.58	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:17:06.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:17:42.91	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 9.1 to above cloud
13:19:00.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 6 at 4800 ft
13:20:48.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:25:48.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:26:56.93	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:27:01.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:01.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:01.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:02.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:27:02.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:02.86	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:27:04.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:27:31.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:28:02.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:30:04.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run descending
13:30:21.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 10
13:31:21.55	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
13:31:43.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
13:32:35.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** now below cloud
13:32:39.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
13:35:49.52	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 50 ft will change to zenith
13:36:14.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
13:36:15.05	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
13:36:16.76	SWS	-5.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:36:18.62	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:36:23.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:23.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:23.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:24.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:24.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:25.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:27.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

13:36:27.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:27.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:27.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:36:28.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:28.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:36:28.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:30.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:36:50.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 7 at 500 ft,
13:36:57.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** below cloud run
13:38:50.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:50.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:50.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:50.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:38:51.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:52.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:38:52.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:38:53.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:46:57.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run, climbing
13:47:17.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 11, climbing towards 3800 ft
13:47:25.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:25.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:25.26	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:26.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:26.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:26.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:28.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:28.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:28.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:47:29.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:30.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:47:30.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:49:14.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base
13:49:18.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
13:49:22.85	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud now
13:50:43.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** run in cloud at 3500 ft
13:50:54.97	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 8
13:52:38.92	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
13:52:44.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:44.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:44.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:45.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:45.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:45.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:47.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:52:48.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:51.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:51.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:51.89	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:52:52.61	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:52.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:52:53.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:54:52.78	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
13:54:54.43	SWS	171.6	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
13:55:02.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:02.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:02.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:03.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:03.91	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:04.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:06.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:06.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:06.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:07.24	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
13:55:07.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:07.46	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
13:55:08.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
13:55:42.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:00:44.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
14:00:56.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top

14:01:12.25	---	-	-	-	*** at top of profile
14:01:12.67	SWS	174.0	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:01:14.36	SWS	-3.9	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:01:25.85	---	-	-	-	*** reversing profile
14:01:34.75	---	-	-	-	*** cloud top
14:02:56.68	---	-	-	-	*** cloud base
14:03:15.76	---	-	-	-	*** descending to 50 ft
14:05:00.08	---	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
14:06:22.24	---	-	-	-	*** 50 ft
14:06:57.84	---	-	-	-	*** run
14:07:01.58	---	-	-	-	*** at 500 ft
14:07:04.29	---	-	-	-	*** run 9
14:07:09.63	---	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:10:25.17	---	-	-	-	*** on long 500 ft leg between P2 and P3
14:12:24.40	---	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:17:38.66	---	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
14:20:08.43	---	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:21:45.86	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:45.88	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:45.92	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:46.67	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:47.04	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:47.54	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:49.99	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
14:21:50.01	USH	-	-	-	Idling
14:21:50.03	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
14:21:52.04	SWS	-6.0	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:21:53.75	SWS	172.9	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:21:54.47	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:54.48	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:54.48	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:56.80	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:56.86	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:56.90	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:21:57.54	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:57.75	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:21:58.66	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:22:45.47	---	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:22:55.55	LSH	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:55.61	USH	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:55.63	SWS	-	-	-	Idling
14:22:57.24	SWS	174.0	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:22:58.94	SWS	-4.0	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:23:00.56	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:00.56	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:00.56	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:02.98	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:03.01	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:03.08	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:23:03.81	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:04.16	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:23:04.64	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:25:27.38	---	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:29:52.77	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:52.82	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:52.89	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:29:53.78	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:53.93	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:29:54.27	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:24.59	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:24.63	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:24.75	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:38:25.60	USH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:25.81	SWS	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:38:26.05	LSH	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:34.76	---	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
14:45:40.03	USH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:40.06	LSH	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:40.08	SWS	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

14:45:40.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:41.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:41.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:43.85	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
14:45:45.57	SWS	172.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:45:48.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:48.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:48.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:49.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:49.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:50.36	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:53.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:53.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:54.01	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:45:54.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:55.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:45:55.60	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:48.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:48.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:48.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
14:46:50.53	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
14:46:52.29	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
14:46:53.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:53.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:53.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:54.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:54.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:54.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:46:55.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:55.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:46:56.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:50:37.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
14:53:19.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
14:56:03.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:04.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:05.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:06.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:08.90	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
14:56:08.91	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
14:56:11.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:11.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:13.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:14.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:25.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:25.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:25.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
14:56:26.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:26.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:56:26.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
14:58:20.12	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:04:15.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:04:21.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:04:49.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction end of run now
15:04:55.68	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
15:05:14.54	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 13 climbing towards 4000ft
15:05:51.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:51.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:51.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:52.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:52.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:53.50	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:56.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:56.33	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:56.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:05:57.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:57.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:05:58.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:07:01.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
15:07:57.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top

15:08:31.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** back in cloud
15:08:36.02	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
15:08:44.72	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
15:08:58.44	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 10 at 3700 ft in cloud run
15:10:10.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:10:39.51	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:11:33.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:11:36.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:37.03	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:37.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:37.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:38.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:38.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:40.60	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
15:11:40.61	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
15:11:45.06	USH	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
15:11:45.07	USH	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 30ms to 20ms.
15:11:47.17	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:47.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:47.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:48.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:48.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:48.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:51.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:51.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:51.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:11:52.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:52.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:11:52.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:18:46.80	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:18:48.53	SWS	173.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:20:16.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:23:43.29	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:23:47.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
15:23:53.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 14.1
15:24:02.22	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing from 3600 ft
15:24:12.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top
15:24:39.07	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:24:40.81	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:24:52.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 14.2 descending
15:24:55.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
15:25:25.21	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud base
15:27:31.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile 14.2 start of profile ascent
15:27:38.84	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:27:55.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** p 14.3 climbing from 1500 ft
15:30:15.28	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
15:30:23.23	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
15:30:32.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 11 at 3700 ft
15:33:11.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:11.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:11.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:12.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:12.75	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:13.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:15.12	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:33:16.86	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:33:20.71	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:20.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:20.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:21.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:21.66	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:21.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:33:22.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:23.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:26.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:26.26	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:26.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:33:26.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:33:27.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:33:28.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:48.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:48.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:48.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:49.38	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:49.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:49.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:51.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:34:53.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:56.02	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:56.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:56.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:34:56.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:57.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:34:57.51	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:05.72	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:35:07.48	SWS	-5.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:35:10.70	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:10.71	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:10.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:35:11.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:11.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:35:12.40	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:44.60	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:37:44.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:37:44.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:37:45.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:45.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:37:46.53	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:39:58.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
15:41:01.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
15:42:26.63	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:26.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:26.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:27.29	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:27.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:28.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:30.27	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:42:32.03	SWS	173.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:42:33.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:33.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:33.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:34.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:34.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:35.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:36.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:36.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:36.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:36.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:37.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:42:37.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:42:38.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:42:43.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:43:12.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
15:44:58.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning
15:45:14.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 11
15:46:08.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
15:46:17.04	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:46:18.72	SWS	-3.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:46:20.74	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:20.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:20.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:21.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:21.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:21.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:23.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:46:25.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:35.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** reversing profile

15:46:43.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:46:43.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:46:43.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:46:44.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:44.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:44.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:46:45.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:46:45.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:46:46.52	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:46:47.52	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:46:50.75	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
15:46:54.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:54.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:54.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:46:54.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:47:12.95	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
15:47:32.65	---	-	-	-	-	*** sws NIR doing some odd things real or not????
15:48:01.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud run
15:48:11.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:11.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:11.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:48:11.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:11.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:48:12.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:49:16.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** correction reversing prforile at 1500 ft
15:49:22.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** climbing back into cloud
15:51:10.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
15:51:17.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
15:51:36.36	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 12 at 3500 ft
15:51:54.75	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:51:54.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:51:54.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:51:55.32	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:55.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:51:56.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:52:28.31	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:53:09.25	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:09.29	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:09.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:53:09.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:10.36	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:53:11.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:02.66	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
15:54:04.45	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:54:06.10	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:06.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:06.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:06.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:07.12	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:07.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:12.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:13.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:13.06	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:13.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:13.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:14.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:18.58	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 30ms.
15:54:18.58	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 30ms.
15:54:20.48	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:21.34	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:54:22.91	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:54:23.68	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:12.41	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
15:55:14.16	SWS	-5.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
15:55:16.16	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:16.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:16.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:16.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

15:55:17.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:17.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:20.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:20.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:20.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:20.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:20.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:55:21.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:55:22.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
15:55:35.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
15:55:40.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** ascending
15:55:53.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:56:10.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** above cloud
15:56:32.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** clear skies above stratocumulus sheet
15:57:00.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
15:57:13.09	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:58:26.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
15:59:06.32	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
15:59:08.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:59:08.69	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:59:08.73	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
15:59:09.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:59:09.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
15:59:10.37	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:01:59.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:02:02.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:02:37.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:03:00.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:04:38.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:05:00.70	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:05:10.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:05:16.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:07:14.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:07:40.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:09:57.20	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:10:04.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:10:16.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:10:21.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:10:43.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
16:18:26.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:26.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:26.88	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:27.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:28.02	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:28.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:29.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:29.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:29.85	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:30.41	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:30.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:31.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:33.76	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:33.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:33.78	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
16:18:34.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:34.80	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
16:18:35.62	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

B418b_SWS_SHIMS_EventLog.txt

```

16:53:19.24 --- - - - -
16:53:19.24 --- - - - - +++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
16:53:19.24 --- - - - - +++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment +++
16:53:19.24 --- - - - - +++ Flight no. B418b
16:53:19.24 --- - - - -
16:53:29.11 SWS - - - - Telescope motor initialised.
16:53:32.85 SWS 0.0 - - - - Telescope sent to -6.000
16:53:33.41 SWS -6.0 - - - - Telescope stopped.
16:53:39.48 SWS - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
16:53:46.93 USH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
16:53:49.86 SWS - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
16:53:57.66 USH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
16:53:59.35 LSH - 100 - - - - Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
16:54:01.02 LSH - - - - Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
16:54:05.58 SWS - - - - 5 NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
16:54:09.07 SWS - - 20 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 20ms.
16:54:09.07 SWS - - - 20 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 20ms.
16:54:11.47 USH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
16:54:14.29 USH - - 30 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
16:54:14.30 USH - - - 30 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 30ms.
16:54:16.25 LSH - - - 5 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
16:54:19.59 LSH - - 50 - - VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
16:54:19.60 LSH - - - 50 - - NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 50ms.
16:54:21.55 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:54:21.56 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:54:21.56 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:54:56.13 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:54:56.15 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:54:56.21 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:54:56.60 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:54:56.79 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
16:54:57.09 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:54:57.20 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:54:57.24 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:54:57.61 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:54:58.28 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
16:55:05.81 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
16:55:13.34 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:55:13.35 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:55:13.35 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:55:14.00 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:55:14.51 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:55:14.54 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:55:15.97 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:55:15.99 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:55:16.03 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
16:55:16.75 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:55:16.83 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:55:17.32 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
16:55:19.79 LSH - - - - Idling
16:55:19.86 USH - - - - Idling
16:55:19.92 SWS - - - - Idling
17:25:26.19 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:25:26.19 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:25:26.20 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:25:30.73 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:25:30.74 LSH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:25:30.82 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:25:30.97 SWS - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
17:25:31.37 SWS - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:25:31.42 USH - - - - Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
17:25:31.87 LSH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:25:31.92 USH - - - - Manual scene recording started.
17:25:33.08 --- - - - - Reset shutters.
17:25:37.00 USH - - - - Dark measurement started.
17:25:37.05 SWS - - - - Dark measurement started.

```

17:25:37.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:25:37.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:37.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:38.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:25:40.18	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:25:40.21	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:25:40.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:33:16.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:16.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:16.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:20.43	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:20.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:20.47	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:33:21.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:21.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:33:21.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:34:12.39	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 90.000
17:34:13.50	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:34:30.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:30.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:30.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:31.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:34:31.04	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:31.32	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:34:32.14	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:34:33.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:33.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:33.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:33.72	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:34:33.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:34:34.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:34:34.56	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:34:37.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:34:37.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:53:15.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:53:15.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:53:24.46	SWS	90.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:53:25.61	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
17:54:18.31	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 100ms.
17:54:18.32	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 100ms.
17:54:21.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:54:21.53	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:54:21.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:54:22.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:54:22.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:54:23.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:54:24.53	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:55:38.98	---	-	-	-	-	
17:55:38.98	---	-	-	-	-	+++ SOFTWARE START/RESTART +++
17:55:38.98	---	-	-	-	-	+++ hh:mm:ss.ff / Instr / Posn / Period /
tVIS/ tNIR / Comment	+++					
17:55:38.98	---	-	-	-	-	+++ Flight no. B418b
17:55:38.98	---	-	-	-	-	
17:55:42.12	SWS	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
17:55:50.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:55:51.48	USH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
17:55:54.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:55:55.62	SWS	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
17:55:59.05	SWS	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
17:55:59.06	SWS	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
17:56:06.15	LSH	-	100	-	-	Sample period changed from 250ms to 100ms.
17:56:06.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Initialization: VIS OK NIR OK
17:56:07.71	USH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
17:56:10.18	USH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
17:56:10.18	USH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
17:56:11.64	LSH	-	-	-	5	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 5ms.
17:56:13.39	LSH	-	-	100	-	VIS int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
17:56:13.39	LSH	-	-	-	100	NIR int.time changed from 5ms to 100ms.
17:56:16.97	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

17:56:16.97	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:16.98	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:17.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
17:56:23.20	USH	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
17:56:23.20	USH	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 30ms.
17:56:27.10	SWS	-	-	20	-	VIS int.time changed from 100ms to 20ms.
17:56:27.11	SWS	-	-	-	20	NIR int.time changed from 100ms to 20ms.
17:56:39.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:39.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:39.45	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:39.65	USH	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
17:56:39.84	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Abnormally bright dark measurement.
17:56:40.12	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:56:40.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:40.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:56:41.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
17:57:53.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:07.70	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:58:14.80	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
17:58:19.46	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:58:19.49	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:58:19.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:58:20.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:20.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:20.95	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:23.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:58:23.19	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:58:23.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:58:23.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:24.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:58:25.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:00.37	SWS	-	-	-	-	Telescope motor initialised.
17:59:03.62	SWS	0.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
17:59:07.54	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:08.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:09.23	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:09.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:12.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
17:59:13.80	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
17:59:35.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 12 deg
18:01:43.60	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
18:08:15.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
18:11:05.81	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:11:10.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
18:11:16.03	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 16
18:12:35.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** entering cloud
18:15:54.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
18:18:06.52	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
18:18:08.20	SWS	170.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
18:18:23.15	---	-	-	-	-	*** at 50 ft changed sws view to nadir
18:18:28.08	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
18:18:31.30	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:31.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:31.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:32.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:32.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:32.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:45.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
18:18:50.30	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 14
18:18:52.33	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:52.33	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:52.35	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:53.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:53.17	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:54.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:54.53	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:54.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:54.63	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:18:55.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

18:18:55.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:55.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:18:56.61	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:18:57.52	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
18:18:59.21	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
18:19:01.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:19:01.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:19:01.64	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:19:02.51	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:19:02.66	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:19:03.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:19:10.30	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:20:15.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:15.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:15.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:16.65	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:20:16.71	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:20:16.82	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:20:18.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
18:23:36.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
18:23:36.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:25:02.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:25:02.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:25:02.82	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:25:03.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:25:03.82	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:25:04.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:25:14.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
18:25:58.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
18:29:05.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:29:12.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
18:29:24.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 17
18:32:28.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
18:33:36.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 18 descending
18:33:58.05	---	-	-	-	-	*** entering cloud
18:39:02.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
18:39:41.51	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
18:39:48.11	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
18:39:55.87	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:39:55.88	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:39:55.89	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:39:56.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:39:57.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:39:57.31	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:41:09.09	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
18:43:14.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
18:44:39.75	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run 15
18:44:49.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of profilr 19
18:44:53.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** descending
18:48:18.40	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 16 at 500 ft
18:51:50.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
18:57:46.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
18:57:57.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile ascent to 4500 ft
18:58:10.70	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 20
18:58:52.08	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
18:59:01.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:01.03	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:01.06	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:01.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:01.95	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:02.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:08.48	SWS	-	-	10	-	VIS int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
18:59:08.48	SWS	-	-	-	10	NIR int.time changed from 20ms to 10ms.
18:59:10.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:10.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:10.64	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:11.14	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:11.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:12.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

18:59:12.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:12.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:12.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:13.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:13.77	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:14.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:15.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:15.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:15.59	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:16.26	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:16.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:16.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:30.43	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
18:59:31.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
18:59:45.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
19:01:05.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
19:01:28.14	---	-	-	-	-	*** leaving cloud
19:01:36.56	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
19:01:49.06	---	-	-	-	-	*** reversing profile
19:02:18.99	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
19:02:39.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
19:02:52.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 at 3600ft
19:03:44.49	---	-	-	-	-	*** moving to 3700 ft
19:04:00.01	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:00.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:00.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:04:00.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:01.21	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:01.49	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:04:57.95	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
19:04:59.66	SWS	172.3	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:05:08.92	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:05:08.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:05:08.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:05:09.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:05:09.94	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:05:10.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:06:41.79	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:06:41.79	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:06:41.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:06:42.35	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:06:42.81	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:06:42.92	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:06:43.56	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:06:43.73	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:06:49.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
19:07:09.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
19:07:29.76	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
19:07:31.46	SWS	-4.9	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:12:41.13	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
19:12:50.53	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent P 22
19:12:57.96	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
19:14:46.20	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
19:16:34.73	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 18 at 500 ft
19:16:50.12	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:50.18	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:50.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:50.93	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:16:50.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:16:51.99	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:16:54.54	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:54.55	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:54.59	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:55.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:16:55.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:16:55.31	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:16:56.74	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:16:58.38	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:16:58.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling

19:16:59.87	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
19:17:01.46	---	-	-	-	-	Reset shutters.
19:17:01.57	SWS	172.4	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:17:04.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:04.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:04.70	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:05.21	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:05.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:07.83	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:07.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:07.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:08.58	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:08.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:09.48	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:44.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:44.04	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:44.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:44.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:45.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:46.00	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:48.32	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:17:48.42	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:17:48.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:17:50.14	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
19:17:52.34	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:17:52.83	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:52.84	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:52.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:55.06	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:55.08	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:55.11	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:17:55.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:56.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:17:56.94	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:18:13.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
19:25:42.90	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
19:26:28.41	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
19:26:43.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climbv
19:27:27.45	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
19:30:07.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** reversing climb
19:30:11.37	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
19:31:07.92	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3700 ft
19:31:42.78	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 19 at 3500 ft in cloud
19:35:19.85	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:19.85	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:19.86	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:20.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:20.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:21.77	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:29.20	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:29.20	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:29.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:29.96	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:30.15	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:30.90	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:35.86	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
19:35:38.60	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
19:35:40.31	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:35:41.50	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:41.52	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:41.56	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:35:42.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:42.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:35:43.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:37:30.94	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
19:37:32.64	SWS	-4.5	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:37:44.26	---	-	-	-	-	*** reaching edge of cloud
19:37:49.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:37:49.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

19:37:50.00	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:37:50.67	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:37:51.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:37:51.44	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:38:39.89	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud breaking up
19:38:49.67	---	-	-	-	-	*** currently in a clear patch
19:38:52.27	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:52.34	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:52.36	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:38:53.07	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:38:53.24	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:38:53.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:38:57.63	SWS	-	-	30	-	VIS int.time changed from 10ms to 30ms.
19:38:57.64	SWS	-	-	-	30	NIR int.time changed from 10ms to 30ms.
19:38:59.96	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:39:00.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:39:00.11	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:39:00.72	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:39:01.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:39:01.63	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:39:02.83	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:39:02.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:39:02.87	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:39:03.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:39:04.00	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:39:04.28	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:39:26.69	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
19:39:52.94	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
19:40:04.80	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile climb
19:40:22.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
19:42:13.00	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
19:42:19.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent
19:42:24.83	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
19:42:26.54	SWS	173.2	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:42:28.09	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:28.14	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:28.16	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:28.55	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:28.81	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:42:29.50	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:42:29.54	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:42:29.78	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:42:32.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:42:32.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:43:38.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
19:47:46.87	---	-	-	-	-	*** run at 500 ft
19:47:52.37	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
19:47:53.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Warning: Clipping may be occurring.
19:47:54.09	SWS	-5.1	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
19:47:55.98	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:47:56.03	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:47:56.05	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:47:56.77	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:47:57.17	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:47:57.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:48:31.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
19:55:55.17	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
19:57:10.18	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
19:57:25.01	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:57:25.07	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:57:25.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:57:25.68	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:57:25.84	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:57:26.43	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
19:57:26.67	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:57:29.07	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:58:15.90	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:58:15.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
19:58:15.97	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

19:58:16.65	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:58:16.90	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:58:17.79	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
19:59:08.64	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
20:00:39.13	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:00:39.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:00:39.22	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:00:40.15	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:00:40.30	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:00:40.66	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:04:48.50	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
20:07:38.38	LSH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:07:38.39	SWS	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:07:38.40	USH	-	-	-	-	Idling
20:07:39.93	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:07:39.93	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:07:39.95	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:10:25.25	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
20:11:08.82	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
20:12:30.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
20:12:36.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** turning
20:13:19.71	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
20:13:23.04	---	-	-	-	-	*** run 20.2
20:19:23.93	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
20:20:07.43	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
20:22:45.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
20:27:58.63	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
20:29:24.46	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
20:30:52.27	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
20:30:54.98	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
20:31:56.48	---	-	-	-	-	*** run
20:32:07.33	---	-	-	-	-	*** start of run 20.3 at 500 ft
20:35:28.42	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:35:28.45	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:35:28.52	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:35:29.39	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:35:29.62	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:35:29.96	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:36:55.76	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
20:43:52.66	---	-	-	-	-	*** 17 deg
20:44:34.62	---	-	-	-	-	*** 16 deg
20:46:34.19	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:46:34.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:46:34.25	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:46:35.19	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:46:35.41	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:46:35.68	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:46:44.11	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
20:48:11.16	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of run
20:49:17.47	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile descent to 50 ft
20:49:37.57	---	-	-	-	-	*** profile 27.1
20:50:06.38	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of p 27.1 start of profile 27.2
ascending from 50 ft						
20:52:01.58	---	-	-	-	-	*** 14 deg
20:52:10.79	---	-	-	-	-	*** in cloud
20:53:18.59	---	-	-	-	-	*** coming out of cloud now
20:53:25.77	---	-	-	-	-	*** cloud top 3500 ft
20:54:47.24	---	-	-	-	-	*** end of profile climb
20:55:28.39	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:55:28.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:55:28.44	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:55:29.42	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:55:29.62	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:55:29.91	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:55:35.88	SWS	-6.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to 174.000
20:55:37.62	SWS	173.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
20:55:40.57	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:55:40.57	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
20:55:40.58	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.

20:55:41.35	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:55:41.73	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:55:42.27	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
20:57:48.61	---	-	-	-	-	*** 13 deg
21:02:29.34	---	-	-	-	-	*** 15 deg
21:02:42.41	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:42.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:42.47	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:43.44	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:43.64	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:43.92	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:45.25	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:45.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:45.34	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:46.31	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:46.46	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:46.89	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:49.80	SWS	174.0	-	-	-	Telescope sent to -6.000
21:02:51.57	SWS	-5.8	-	-	-	Telescope stopped.
21:02:53.09	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:53.10	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:53.15	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:53.87	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:54.13	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:55.05	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:57.18	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:57.23	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:57.27	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:02:57.94	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:58.40	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:02:58.88	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:25.76	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:25.78	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:25.80	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:26.74	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:27.04	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:27.22	LSH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:27.99	USH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:28.05	SWS	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:28.08	LSH	-	-	-	-	Dark measurement started.
21:21:28.76	USH	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.
21:21:28.99	SWS	-	-	-	-	Manual scene recording started.

B418 LWC run 5

B418 LWC run 10

B418 LWC run 8 and P12

B418 LWC run 10-11 and P15

B418 LWC run 17

B418 qv profiles 2nd part

B418 nep scattering runs20

B418 tephi P1

B418 tephi P2P4 and into R2

B418 tephi P2

B418 tephi P7

B418 tephi P10

B418 tephi P23

B418 tephi P11

B418 tephi P27

B418 theta profiles 2nd part

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B418:

Log	Reason
Cloud Physics Processing	No cloud physics processing logs are expected for VOCALS flights
Core Chemistry / TDLAS	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
Dry Neph	Operator does not create a log sheet
2D-S / CAPS	2D-S / CAPS operator does not create a log sheet
AMS log	AMS operator does not create a log sheet
PAN log	PAN operator does not create a log sheet
VACC	Operator does not create a log sheet

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Sep 2009	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

Digital video recordings in avi format:

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_113349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_123349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_133349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_143349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_153349_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_185246_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_195246_1hz.avi
 faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_205246_1hz.avi

faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_113343_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_123343_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_133343_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_143343_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_153343_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_175241_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_185241_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_195241_1hz.avi
 faam-video-rfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_205241_1hz.avi

faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_113341_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_123341_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_133341_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_143341_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_153341_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_175240_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_185240_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_195240_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ffc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_205240_1hz.avi

faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_113346_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_123346_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_133346_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_143346_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_153346_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_175243_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_185243_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_195243_1hz.avi
 faam-video-ufc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_205243_1hz.avi

faam-video-dfc_faam_20081110_r0_b418_175246_1hz.raw failed to convert at I Frame 438

No Digital8 video recordings were made on this flight.